

inspire
SMART VILLAGE LABS

D7.3 Data Management Plan – First

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Executive Summary

The present document constitutes the initial version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the INSPIRE project, funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme. The INSPIRE project contributes to sustainable and inclusive development of European rural areas by promoting social wellbeing and inclusion of rural dwellers and vulnerable groups and enhancing governance frameworks in rural areas. In particular, the project contributes to advancing in a multi-dimensional way the concept of social inclusion in rural areas, and supports the access to high-quality social services by rural citizens through a series of awareness raising, capacity building, and pilot deployment activities that focus on social entrepreneurship and improvement of social services in a set of 7 different pilot territories (e.g., coastal, rural, peri-urban, mountainous). To realise its objectives, the project provides a novel territorial typology of rural areas, sets up and operationalises 7 "Smart Village labs", and enhances governance frameworks and informed policy making through E-Democracy and user-innovation techniques, to eventually deliver a dedicated Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard.

In this context, this version of the INSPIRE Data Management Plan describes the data management processes to be followed during the lifecycle of the project, along with the methodology employed in order to ensure the FAIR provisions for data management. It builds on the GDPR guidelines and provides information about the data to be collected/generated throughout the project activities, as well as details about the procedures to be followed in order to make this data openly accessible. Finally, it defines the data management responsibilities, sets the premises on data security and provides an estimation of the resources to be allocated, so as to make the data FAIR.

This version of the INSPIRE Data Management Plan sets a basic framework of necessary actions, as perceived at this stage of the project. In this respect, the DMP will be further elaborated and updated by the end of the project, in order to depict any changes in the data that needs to be collected or any modifications in the data processing tools and methods, among others. Finally, it is complemented by Work Package seven (WP7) deliverables, which cover ethical considerations in more detail.

Disclaimer:

The methodology for the data management plan of the INSPIRE project (GA No. 101136592) draws upon established expertise, tools, and templates developed internally by White Research SRL, while also considering European Commission guidelines and best practices found in relevant literature. Elements of this methodology have been refined through previous Horizon projects where White Research was involved as project coordinator, such as MOBI-TWIN (GA No. 101094402) and BECoop (GA No. 952930). This approach ensures efficient resource utilisation and alignment with project specifications. Customised adjustments were made to accommodate INSPIRE's unique requirements, EU recommendations and Grant Agreement conditions. This report outlines the adapted methodology as it was further developed and implemented within INSPIRE.

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List of Terms and Definitions

Table 1. Terms and Definitions

Abbreviation	Definition
AB	Advisory Board
CA	Consortium Agreement
EC or Commission	European Commission
DM	Dissemination Manager
DMP	Data Management Plan
EU	European Union
EM	Ethics Mentor
GAs	General Assembly
GA	Grant Agreement
IM	Innovation Manager
MQP	Management & Quality Plan
PC	Project Coordinator
PMO	Project Management Office
PO	Project Officer
QM	Quality Manager
SC	Scientific Coordinator
SE	Social Economy
TL	Task Leader
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

1. Introduction

1.1 Overview and objectives

INSPIRE seeks to promote social inclusion, wellbeing, and prosperity in European rural areas through a blend of research, pilot innovation, and policy interventions. The project uses advanced methodologies and pilot deployment activities, including a multi-disciplinary conceptual framework of social inclusion that combines Computational Social Sciences with traditional data collection methods (e.g., ethnographic fieldwork) to cover hard-to-reach populations. The project also creates an advanced territorial typology of rural areas in Europe, providing information about social inclusion drivers, status, risks, and trends. In addition, it fosters social inclusion and empowerment by analysing successful service programmes, initiatives and policies, and developing the Services and Social Economy Atlas on Rural Empowerment.

Based on the “Smart Village” concept, INSPIRE enhances governance frameworks for social inclusion (Smart Village labs) through accompanied interventions in 7 pilot areas, which represent diverse settings (rural, coastal, peri-urban, mountainous, etc.) and target groups in vulnerable situations. These labs connect multiple actors in rural economy value chains (including groups in vulnerable situations), provide capacity-building training in various skills, support user innovation, smart specialisation, and E-democracy principles and enhance industry-academia-state collaboration. The project tests real social economy solutions to enhance access to services as well as to boost their local business ecosystem, while delivering concrete evidence on strengths, limitations, suitability, and potentials of social economy.

Finally, the project develops the Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard to support informed policymaking, nurture social entrepreneurship in rural Europe, and ensure social inclusion and access of vulnerable groups to services. The project's methodology will be outlined in a Replication Guidebook and Toolkit for other cases to follow, paving the way for stronger, connected, prosperous, and resilient rural areas.

In this context, the main objectives of the INSPIRE project are to:

- Provide a thorough understanding of social inclusion concept, trends and challenges in rural areas by merging advanced and traditional complementary research methodologies to integrate hard-to-reach populations and tackle current research limitations.
- Mapping, analysing, and benchmarking (social) service programmes, policies and initiatives, as well as social economy (SE) and social entrepreneurial models to understand advantages, potential and limitations and to deliver a Services and Social Economy Atlas on Rural Empowerment for policy support.
- Enhance existing governance frameworks for social inclusion and social economy in rural areas by establishing Smart Village Labs for multi-actor engagement and user innovation.
- Identify, co-develop, pilot and evaluate novel social economy solutions for enhancing social inclusion and economic prosperity in rural areas through better access to quality services.
- Equip policy makers with research and implementation tools (e.g., user-innovation methods, modules, E-Democracy tools) and policy recommendations towards the support of social

inclusion, access of vulnerable groups in services and uptake of rural SE through a dedicated Guidebook.

To achieve the objectives above, a multidisciplinary and well-balanced consortium has been assembled, possessing wide access to relevant groups in vulnerable situations and rural stakeholders. The consortium of INSPIRE consists of 18 partners, coming from 11 different European countries, as summarised in **Error! Reference source not found.2**.

Table 2. INSPIRE partners

#	Role	Partner name	Short name	Country
1	Coordinator	WHITE RESEARCH SRL	WR	Belgium
2	Contractor	RIJKSUNIVERSITEIT GRONINGEN	RUG	The Netherlands
3	Contractor	UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA	UB	Spain
4	Contractor	KENTRO EREVNON NOTIOANATOLIKIS EVROPIS ASTIKI MI KERDOSKOPIKI ETAIREIA	SEERC	Greece
5	Contractor	CESKA ZEMEDELSKA UNIVERZITA V PRAZE	CZU	Czechia
6	Contractor	KOC UNIVERSITY	KOC	Turkey
7	Contractor	SOCIAL ECONOMY EUROPE	SEE	Belgium
8	Contractor	EUROPEAN ASSOCIATION OF SERVICE PROVIDERS FOR PERSONS WITH DISABILITIES	EASPD	Belgium
9	Contractor	EUROPEAN SOCIAL NETWORK	ESN	Belgium
10	Contractor	RESEAU EUROPEEN DES FEMMES MIGRANTES	ENMW	Belgium
11	Contractor	PEDAL CONSULTING	PEDAL	Slovakia
12	Contractor	EUROPEAN RURAL DEVELOPMENT NETWORK	ERDN	Poland
13	Contractor	MESOGIAXO INSTITOUTO GIA TI FYSI KAI TON ANTHROPO- ASTIKI MI KERDOSKOPIKI ETAIREIA	MEDINA	Greece
14	Contractor	L'ADAPT	L'ADAPT	France
15	Contractor	ROTHA T/A THE WHEEL	WHEEL	Ireland
16	Contractor	ASOCIATA NATIONALA PENTRU DEZVOLTARE RURALA MONTANA ROMONTANA	ROM	Romania
17	Contractor	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS	Q-PLAN	Greece
18	Contractor	ARX NET AE YPIRESIES KAI EPICHIRISIS DIADIKTYOY ANONIMI ETAIRIA	ARX.NET	Greece

In this context, **all partners of the INSPIRE consortium adhere to sound data management principles** in order to ensure that the meaningful data collected, processed and/or generated throughout the duration of the project are well-managed, archived and preserved, in line with the Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon Europe and the General Data Protection Regulation

(GDPR). Along these lines, **this first version of the DMP aims to achieve the following objectives:**

- ✓ Describe the data management lifecycle for the data collected and/or generated in the framework of INSPIRE, serving as the key element of good data management.
- ✓ Outline the methodology employed to safeguard the sound management of the data collected, and/or generated, as well as to make them FAIR.
- ✓ Provide information on the data that is collected and/or generated and the way in which it is handled during and after the end of the project along with the standards applied to this end.
- ✓ Describe details on how the data will be made openly accessible and searchable to interested stakeholders, as well as its curation and preservation.

Present information on the resources to be allocated to make data FAIR, clearly identifying the responsibilities pertaining to data management and considering data security across the entire lifetime of data.

1.2 Structure

This first version of **the DMP is structured in 6 distinct chapters**, as follows:

- **Chapter 1** outlines the purpose and objectives of the INSPIRE activities that lead to the collection and/or generation of datasets. In addition, it presents data types and formats, origin, expected volume and relevant stakeholders that might utilise the data.
- **Chapter 2** describes the processes followed to ensure FAIR data management during the entire lifecycle of the INSPIRE project.
- **Chapter 3** provides an estimation of the resources required to ensure FAIR data management and defines the respective responsibilities.
- **Chapter 4** outlines the data security strategy followed by INSPIRE, along with the implemented secure storage procedures.
- **Chapter 5** addresses ethical aspects regarding the collected/generated data.
- **Chapter 6** summarises the conclusions of this document.

The Annex section provides the necessary documentation with regard to the INSPIRE activities' consent procedures, namely:

- ❖ INSPIRE Privacy Policy;
- ❖ INSPIRE Information Sheet and Informed Consent Form;
- ❖ INSPIRE Data Subject Request form.

The DMP is not a fixed document. It evolves during the lifespan of the project and will be **further elaborated and updated by the end of the INSPIRE project. Additional ad hoc updates may also be realised (if necessary)**, in order to include new data, better detail and/or reflect changes in the methodology or other aspects relevant to their management (such as costs for making data FAIR, size of data, etc.), changes in consortium policies and plans or other potential external factors. WR is responsible for the elaboration of the DMP and, with the support of all partners, will update and enrich it whenever required.

2. Data summary

To achieve its purpose, the initial scope of INSPIRE is set to collect, generate and re-use non-sensitive data that are not included into any special categories of personal data as those are described within the GDPR. As people in a vulnerable situation are expected to largely participate in data collection activities (research and engagement), INSPIRE has appointed a dedicated Ethics Mentor to advise, share experience and knowledge on how to properly identify and address ethics issues, as well as to keep reports of the activities performed. The Mentor will mostly provide support to the 6 pilot partners of the project (ERDN, PEDAL, MEDINA, LADAPT, WHEEL, ROM) to ensure that all data collection procedures will avoid scientific misconduct. The relevant information is described in the Management and Quality Plan of the project (D7.1).

This data comprises of quantitative, qualitative or a mixture of both and will be analysed from different perspectives and methodological approaches to provide insights that will successfully meet INSPIRE's activities. In addition, utilisation of this dataset will be imperative to satisfy and fulfil the project's objectives. Any type of personal data collected will be handled in accordance with the GDPR regulation. This chapter of the Data Management Plan (DMP) defines the **purpose of the data collected/generated** under the framework of INSPIRE along with a detailed **description of data types and formats, data origins and expected size**. It concludes with an overview of data utility and potential stakeholders that might find the data useful for reuse.

2.1 Purpose of the data collection/generation and relation to the objectives of the project

The successful satisfaction of the INSPIRE objectives requires several activities under which a battery of data will be collected and generated. In this context, each data collecting/generating process, is matched to the respective objective and activity of the project that corresponds.

The **main activities of the INSPIRE data collection/generation process** along with their objectives are the following:

- **Systematic review on social exclusion in rural areas:** Through a systematic review of academic journals, policy reports, previous research frameworks, and relevant studies focusing on rural vulnerabilities, we will re-define and conceptualise social exclusion in rural areas and develop a methodological framework for measurement.
- **Delphi exercise for forecast of trends and drivers of social exclusion in rural areas:** Through a Delphi exercise, we will collect primary data on expected mega-trends and drivers of social exclusion across rural Europe.
- **National survey on social exclusion:** Through a large-scale quantitative survey, we will collect primary data to uncover nation-wide challenges faced by rural dwellers (e.g., gender bias, skills gaps, political exclusion) and needs.
- **National interviews with QH stakeholders:** Through semi-structured interviews with Quadruple Helix stakeholder interviews, we will collect primary data on different angles of the most important national challenges of rural areas for social inclusion.

- **Observational fieldwork in pilot areas:** Through techniques of traditional observational fieldwork and ethnographic research, we will collect micro-level information on community and individual specificities regarding social exclusion in each pilot area.
- **CATI surveys for micro-level data:** Through CATI surveys in the 7 pilot areas, we will collect primary data on micro-level factors that drive social exclusion across rural Europe.
- **Paper-based surveys for micro-level data:** Through complementary paper-based, on-site surveys in the 7 pilot areas, we will collect primary data on micro-level factors that drive social exclusion across rural Europe.
- **Typology on social wellbeing, resilience and exclusion of European rural areas:** By re-integrating and using the datasets generated under WP1 data collection activities, we will develop a new territorial classification of European rural areas on social wellbeing.
- **Desk research on social services and social inclusion in Europe:** Through a combination of literature review, document analysis, data mapping, we will collect secondary data and develop a database on rural social services and legal frameworks.
- **Semi-structured interviews with policy stakeholders:** Through semi-structured interviews with regional and local policymakers, service providers, and other stakeholders, we will gather qualitative insights on social inclusion policies, service challenges, and successful practices.
- **Focus groups for evaluation of social services:** Through group discussions with end-users and service providers, we will produce data regarding the evaluation of identified social services, as well as about their effectiveness, accessibility, and sustainability.
- **Conceptual definitions, legal frameworks and impact frameworks of social economy in the EU:** Through desk research, we will collect secondary data on the conceptual definitions and legal frameworks for the social economy from EU Member States. Moreover, we will gather existing impact frameworks at global, EU and national level to evaluate social economy services with the aim of assessing them and developing impact indicators.
- **Digital ethnography:** By deploying digital ethnographic research and integrating results from desk research and observational fieldwork, we will capture primary data on social enterprise activities and their impact, aiming to cover isolated and remote areas that often remain outside the research microscope.
- **Microsimulation – Agent Based Modelling:** Through spatial microsimulation based on a social exclusion survey, agent based modelling based on digital ethnography, we will design agent-based models on social interactions and the role of social enterprises in rural areas.
- **Territorial profiling of pilot areas: needs assessment and vulnerability assessment:** Through desk research of secondary databases, grey literature and academic journals, observational fieldwork, as well as through consultation with pilot partners, we will develop a detailed profile of each pilot area. We will also identify key vulnerable groups, local challenges and stakeholders in each pilot area to develop a tailored local engagement plan.
- **Local awareness raising campaigns in 7 pilot areas:** Through the deployment of various data collection methods, we will produce concrete analytics of local awareness raising campaigns in the 7 pilot locales.
- **Local co-creation workshops on Smart Village Labs in 7 pilot areas:** Through the use of various data collection methods (e.g., registration list of participants, taking photos, video-recording), we will produce concrete analytics of local creation workshops in the pilot sites.
- **User-innovation workshop 1:** Through workshop facilitation techniques (e.g., minutes keeping) we will document records of participants' attendance, discussions, and decisions made during the first round of pilot workshops.

- **User-innovation workshop 2:** Through workshop facilitation techniques (e.g., minutes keeping) we will document records of participants' attendance, discussions, and decisions made during the second round of pilot workshops.
- **Sustaining the Smart Village labs and identifying key stakeholder participants:** By organising and implementing labs' local sustainability workshops, we will produce data on co-creating a roadmap and Memorandum of collaboration to sustain the labs after the end of the project.
- **Results of training programmes (MOOCs):** Through a combination of needs assessment and planning, as well as through active learning techniques, we will produce the INSPIRE MOOC, which will be stored in various formats to suit the diverse content types and platform requirements.
- **Needs assessment of lab participants:** Through structured questionnaires, we will identify the needs of lab participants. It will also help us identify common themes and areas requiring targeted support.
- **Field visits and case studies:** Through observational fieldwork, we will produce insights from field visits to successful social economy initiatives. This dataset will help us provide valuable lessons and best practices that participants can adapt to their projects.
- **Co-Design sessions:** Through a combination of note-taking, photographic documentation, surveys, and post-session interviews, we will produce evidence about the results from interactive sessions where participants, experts, and stakeholders collaboratively develop prototypes and solutions.
- **Two-day cross-territorial networking event:** Through a combination of note-taking, photographic documentation, surveys, and post-session interviews, we will produce evidence about the results from the two-day cross-territorial networking event.
- **Pilot and scale up demonstration report:** By deploying on the ground observations and collecting verbal feedback from pilot participants about the immediate operational interventions and outcomes from the 7 pilot cases.
- **Quantitative data collection for evaluation of Smart Village Labs' impact:** Through various quantitative instruments (e.g., digital quizzes, online survey, on-site survey), we will capture, measure and demonstrate the short-term impact of the pilot innovation activities that take place under the Smart Village Labs.
- **Qualitative data collection for evaluation of Smart Village Labs' impact:** Through various qualitative instruments (e.g., explanatory face-to-face interviews), we might follow-up to explain the quantitative results whenever and if needed.
- **Network of Interest stakeholder engagement:** Through stakeholder interviews, surveys, and desk research, we will collect data on stakeholder contact and profile information to establish the project's Network of Interest.
- **Network interaction records:** We will use documentation from meeting minutes, online platform interactions, and feedback forms from participants to showcase records on stakeholder meetings, workshops, and collaborative sessions to understand network dynamics.
- **Creation of the Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard:** Through integration of results from prior tasks (e.g., territorial typology, the Services and Social Economy Atlas, and policy recommendations) into a unified dashboard, we will produce a Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard Dataset: a user-friendly dashboard for supporting informed rural policy-making and governance.

- **Replication of INSPIRE activities in follower cases:** Through notes and excel files retrieved from replication activities of the project, we will produce evidence about the replication of INSPIRE activities in follower cases.
- **Monitoring and assessment of the website's dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement activities:** We will generate website analytics and data on newsletter subscriptions through Google Analytics and Mailchimp (respectively), which will demonstrate the impact of the website outreach. This type of information will be mostly used for reporting purposes.
- **Monitoring and assessment of the social media dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement activities:** We will produce quantitative social media statistics through the analytics of the project's various social media channels (e.g., LinkedIn, Facebook) with a view to measuring and assessing the performance and results of the project's social media activity in terms of dissemination and communication.
- **Monitoring and assessment of dissemination and communication activities and events:** By deploying dedicated dissemination reporting templates, we will collect partners' input about individual dissemination activities and their impact (e.g., social media activities, participation in external events).
- **Project synergies identification and engagement:** Through a combination of desk research, literature review, and semi-structured interviews with partners and representatives from identified projects, we will generate a project synergies database.
- **Data generated through management and coordination actions:** Data collected from the project partners in order to coordinate the project.

2.2 Types and formats of collected/generated data

INSPIRE is set to utilise collected/generated data of different structure and format. As a result, data definition process can be based on the source and the physical format of the data¹. In this respect, we can define two main aspects: (i) the process under which the underlying data are created/captured, which includes electronic texts documents, spreadsheets, questionnaires, and transcripts, among others and (ii) the storage format of quantitative and qualitative data. Examples of this aspect include easily accessible formats, such as postscripts (e.g., .pdf, .xps), machine readable formats (e.g., .xml, .html), spreadsheets (e.g., .xlsx, .csv), text documents (e.g., .docx, .doc, .rtf), compressed formats (e.g., .rar, .zip) or any other format required by the objectives and methodology of the activity within the frame of which is produced.

Under this framework, special attention will be paid in using **open formats**² (such as .csv, .pdf, .zip, etc.) and/or **machine-readable formats**³ (such as .xml, .json, .rdf, .html, etc.) when possible, in order to enhance the **interoperability** and **re-use** of INSPIRE's data. In doing so, we will be providing data that is **easily readable** and **freely usable in any software programme** employed by third parties interested in utilising the data.

¹ Jakobsson, U., Braukmann, R., Lundgren M., Expert Tour Guide on Data Management. Retrieved from: <https://www.cessda.eu/Research-Infrastructure/Training/Expert-Tour-Guide-on-Data-Management/1.-Plan>.

² According to the [Open Data Handbook](#): "An open format is a file format with no restrictions, monetary or otherwise, placed upon its use and can be fully processed with at least one free/open-source software tool and it is not encumbered by any copyrights, patents, trademarks or other restrictions so that anyone may use it".

³ According to the [Open Data Handbook](#): "Machine readable formats are file formats that can be automatically read and processed by a computer. Machine-readable data must be structured data".

The following section lists the main activities that entail data collection/ generation, along with their purpose and data description, data source, data origin, storage format, and data expected size.

2.2.1 WP1 Data collection/generation activities

Activity 1	Systematic review on social exclusion in rural areas
Purpose	To re-define and conceptualise social exclusion in rural areas and develop a methodological framework for measurement. The activity aims to gather secondary information on measuring social exclusion, studying relevant domains, defining exclusion thresholds, and identifying optimal tools with a focus on rural vulnerabilities. The output will support further tasks in WP1.
Task / Task Leader	T1.1 / SEERC
Data	Social Exclusion in Rural Areas – Measurement Framework
Data collection/generation process	Systematic review
Data origin	Academic journals, policy reports, previous research frameworks, and relevant studies focusing on rural vulnerabilities
Storage format	.docx, .pdf
Expected data size	Less than 1 GB
Other useful information	A virtual validation workshop will be held to calibrate the conceptual and methodological framework with expert partners.

Activity 2	Forecast of trends and drivers of social exclusion in rural areas
Purpose	A Delphi questionnaire to gather forecasts, through an exercise involving EU-wide experts on social inclusion and rural development (≥ 50), focusing on the social inclusion needs of a variety of rural areas, the needs of vulnerable groups, the impact on access in service delivery and on social entrepreneurship, as well as the governance mitigation measures.
Task / Task Leader	T1.2 / Q-PLAN
Data	Delphi questionnaire results on social exclusion forecast
Data collection/generation process	Delphi questionnaire
Data origin	Delphi exercise participants (experts on social inclusion and rural development)
Storage format	.docx, .xlsx, .pdf
Expected data size	100 MB
Other useful information	The Data will be collected through a web platform in two rounds. Q-PLAN will apply the necessary anonymisation procedures to anonymise the data in such a way that the data subject is no longer identifiable.

Activity 3	Identification of expert participants for the Delphi exercise
Purpose	Identify and shortlist the experts on social inclusion and rural development who will be invited to participate in the Delphi questionnaire.
Task / Task Leader	T1.2 / Q-PLAN
Data	Data on Delphi exercise participants
Data collection/generation process	Consortium partners' networks, online search of experts
Data origin	Consortium partners, web sources
Storage format	.xlsx
Expected data size	30 MB
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 4	National survey on social exclusion
Purpose	The survey is used to uncover national factors that create challenges faced by rural dwellers (e.g., gender bias, skills gaps, political exclusion) and needs.

Task / Task Leader	T1.3 / RUG
Data	Social exclusion survey
Data collection/generation process	Survey
Data origin	Survey conducted by pilot partners
Storage format	RUG Qualtrics Environment, .csv in RUG protected data storage drive (two factor authenticated)
Expected data size	Less than 1 GB
Other useful information	The surveys will be administered by the pilot partners. The pilot partners will have access to their own Qualtrics questionnaire for the duration of the data gathering. Subsequent access to the raw data will be restricted to RUG project-related staff.

Activity 5	National interviews with QH stakeholders
Purpose	First, semi-structured interviews (coordinated by RUG and performed by pilot partners) will be implemented to reflect on different angles of the most important national challenges of rural areas for social inclusion.
Task / Task Leader	T1.3 / RUG
Data	Quadruple Helix stakeholder interviews
Data collection/generation process	Semi-structured interviews
Data origin	Interviewed stakeholders, pilot areas
Storage format	.docx, audio files, in RUG protected data storage drive (two factor authenticated)
Expected data size	Less than 1 GB
Other useful information	Data will be collected by pilot regions and transferred to RUG. Subsequent access will be limited to RUG project-related staff.

Activity 6	Observational fieldwork in pilot areas
Purpose	To get micro-level information on community and individual specificities regarding social exclusion in each pilot area
Task / Task Leader	T1.4 / UB
Data	Data from observational fieldwork in pilot areas
Data collection/generation process	Techniques of traditional observational fieldwork and ethnographic research
Data origin	Inhabitants and rural dwellers of targeted communities in the pilot areas
Storage format	.docx, .jpg, .png, .mp4 (video recordings), .mp3 (audio recordings, with consent)
Expected data size	More than 5 GB
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 7	CATI surveys for micro-level data
Purpose	To get micro-level information on community and individual specificities regarding social exclusion in each pilot area
Task / Task Leader	T1.4 / UB
Data	CATI surveys
Data collection/generation process	Computer-Assisted Telephone Interviewing (CATI) surveys carried out by Pilot partners
Data origin	Answers from CATI surveys
Storage format	.csv
Expected data size	Less than 1 GB
Other useful information	30 answers x 7 pilots = 210 answers in total

Activity 8	Paper-based surveys for micro-level data
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Purpose	To get micro-level information on community and individual specificities regarding social exclusion in each pilot area
Task / Task Leader	T1.4 / UB
Data	Paper-based surveys
Data collection/generation process	Surveys carried out by pilot partners through observational fieldwork
Data origin	Answers from paper-based surveys through observational fieldwork
Storage format	.csv
Expected data size	Less than 1 GB
Other useful information	20 answers x 7 pilots = 140 answers in total

Activity 9	Typology on social wellbeing, resilience and exclusion of European rural areas
Purpose	Develop a new territorial classification of European rural areas on social wellbeing
Task / Task Leader	T1.5 / UB
Data	Typology of rural areas
Data collection/generation process	Integration and re-interpretation of data collected at European, national, and local levels to sketch the profiles of rural areas which will be further clustered into concise groups of territories
Data origin	Research work
Storage format	.csv
Expected data size	Less than 1 GB
Other useful information	N/A

2.2.2 WP2 Data collection/generation activities

Activity 1	Desk Research
Purpose	To explore and define social services, legal frameworks, and social inclusion challenges in rural Europe.
Task / Task Leader	T2.1 / ESN
Data	INSPIRE Rural Social Services and Legal Framework Database
Data collection/generation process	Literature review, document analysis, data mapping
Data origin	Web sources, academic literature, official EU and national documents
Storage format	.docx, .pdf, .xlsx
Expected data size	Less than 1 GB
Other useful information	Includes metadata on service objectives, providers, and outcomes.

Activity 2	Semi Structured Interviews
Purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To gather qualitative insights from stakeholders on social inclusion policies, service challenges, and successful practices. Identify gaps and opportunities in social inclusion services. Highlight best practices for rural service delivery. Provide contextual depth to desk research findings. Inform the development of the "Atlas" and policy recommendations.
Task / Task Leader	T2.1 / ESN
Data	INSPIRE Stakeholder Interview Dataset
Data collection/generation process	Regional and local policymakers, service providers, and other stakeholders
Data origin	.docx, .mp3 (audio recordings, with consent)
Storage format	.docx, .pdf, web links
Expected data size	Less than 5 GB
Other useful information	Anonymised quotes and aggregated insights will be used in reports.

Interview scripts standardised across partners to ensure consistency.

Activity 3	Focus Groups
Purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To evaluate identified social services through qualitative input from end-users and service providers. Assess service effectiveness, accessibility, and sustainability. Identify strengths and weaknesses in social inclusion initiatives. Inform the development of the "Atlas" and policy recommendations.
Task / Task Leader	T2.1 / ESN
Data	INSPIRE Focus Group Dataset
Data collection/generation process	Group discussions with end-users and service providers
Data origin	Focus group participants from pilot areas
Storage format	.docx, .mp3 (audio recordings, with consent)
Expected data size	Less than 5 GB
Other useful information	Each focus group includes 4 end-users and 4 providers. Discussions anonymised in final datasets to protect privacy.

Activity 4	Conceptual definitions and legal frameworks of social economy in the EU
Purpose	To gather the conceptual definitions and legal frameworks for the social economy from all EU Member States clustered on the same way as T2.1
Task / Task Leader	T2.2 / SEE
Data	Definitions and legal frameworks
Data collection/generation process	Desk research
Data origin	Web sources
Storage format	.pdf
Expected data size	Less than 1 GB
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 5	Impact frameworks at global, EU and national level to evaluate social economy services
Purpose	To gather existing impact frameworks at global, EU and national level to evaluate social economy services with the aim of assessing them and developing impact indicators
Task / Task Leader	T2.2 / SEE
Data	Impact frameworks
Data collection/generation process	Desk research
Data origin	Web sources
Storage format	.pdf
Expected data size	Less than 1 GB
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 6	Digital Ethnography
Purpose	RUG will deploy digital ethnographic research to capture primary data on Social Enterprise activities and their impact, aiming to cover isolated and remote areas that often remain outside the research microscope.
Task / Task Leader	T2.3 / RUG
Data	Digital Ethnography
Data collection/generation process	Desk research, semi-structured interviews, observational fieldwork, digital ethnography
Data origin	Web sources, interviewed stakeholders

Storage format	.docx, web links, .xlsx
Expected data size	Less than 1 GB
Other useful information	Access will be limited to RUG project-related staff.

Activity 7	Microsimulation – Agent Based Modelling
Purpose	Spatial microsimulation will be used to create high resolution data on inclusion from the survey in T1.3. Together with the data from the digital ethnographies on how individuals interact with social enterprises, these data will be used to design agent-based models on social interactions and the role of social enterprises in rural areas.
Task / Task Leader	T2.3 / RUG
Data	Spatial microsimulation and agent based modelling
Data collection/generation process	Spatial microsimulation based on “Social Exclusion Survey” (T1.3), agent based modelling based on “Digital Ethnography” (T2.3)
Data origin	Social exclusion survey (T1.3), Eurostat and similar regional datasets, Digital ethnography (T2.3)
Storage format	.Rda, .RData, .gpkg, .pdf in RUG protected data storage drive (two factor authenticated)
Expected data size	Less than 5 GB
Other useful information	N/A

2.2.3 WP3 Data collection/generation activities

Activity 1	Pilot Area Environmental and Needs Assessment
Purpose	Develop a detailed profile of each pilot area by collecting and analysing existing information to understand the local environment, challenges and opportunities affecting services and social enterprises in these areas.
Task / Task Leader	T3.1 / CZU
Data	Territorial profiles of pilot sites
Data collection/generation process	Secondary databases, grey literature and academic journals, observational fieldwork
Data origin	Web sources, Interview with pilot partners, data portals or stat hubs
Storage format	.docx, .pdf, meetings minutes via read Ai (whenever applicable), Numerical/statistical (.xls), social media (text), audio-visual (multimedia)
Expected data size	More than 1 GB
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 2	Targeted Community Engagement and Vulnerability Assessment
Purpose	Identify key vulnerable groups, local challenges and stakeholders in each pilot area to develop a tailored local engagement plan.
Task / Task Leader	T3.1 / CZU
Data	Territorial profiles of pilot sites
Data collection/generation process	Secondary databases, grey literature and academic journals, observational fieldwork
Data origin	Web sources, Interview with pilot partners, data portals or stat hubs
Storage format	.docx, .pdf, meetings minutes via read Ai (whenever applicable), numerical/statistical (.xls), social media (text), audio-visual (multimedia)
Expected data size	More than 1 GB
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 3	Local awareness raising campaigns in 7 pilot areas
Purpose	The campaigns aim to raise awareness of local audiences and stakeholder about the project’s vision, present research results, and engage key

	stakeholders, eventually setting the ground for the co-creation of Smart Village Labs.
Task / Task Leader	T3.2 / WR
Data	Analytics of local awareness raising campaigns (e.g., number of participants in local fairs, analytics of social media campaigns).
Data collection/generation process	Various data collection methods: e.g., registration list of participants, social media analytics.
Data origin	Local audiences and targeted stakeholders in pilot areas
Storage format	.docx, .xlsx, .mpg, .jpg, .mp4
Expected data size	Between 1 and 3 GB
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 4	Local co-creation workshops on Smart Village Labs in 7 pilot areas
Purpose	The workshops will enable targeted stakeholders and representatives of vulnerable groups to co-define the structure, mission, and governance framework of their local Smart Village Lab.
Task / Task Leader	T3.2 / WR
Data	Analytics of local creation workshops (e.g., number of participants in the workshop, video and photo evidence).
Data collection/generation process	Various data collection methods: e.g., registration list of participants, taking photos, video-recording.
Data origin	Local audiences and targeted stakeholders in pilot areas
Storage format	.docx, .xlsx, .mpg, .jpg, .mp4
Expected data size	Between 1 and 3 GB
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 5	User-innovation workshop 1
Purpose	This activity is intended for workshop participants, who will also become members of the labs, to identify, prioritise, and determine local services that need support, especially for the empowerment of vulnerable groups.
Task / Task Leader	T3.3 / MedINA
Data	User-innovation workshop 1 data
Data collection/generation process	Workshop facilitators will document the minutes of the workshop and take photos of participants in action.
Data origin	The documentation will include records of participants' attendance, discussions, and decisions made during the workshop.
Storage format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • docx and pdf for the minutes of the workshop • jpeg for the images of participants in action
Expected data size	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less than 25 MB (up to 3 MB per pilot area) • Less than 700 MB (up to 100 MB per pilot area)
Other useful information	To safeguard participants' privacy, real names will be substituted with fictitious ones. Additionally, upon request, the faces of participants in images may be blurred.

Activity 6	User-innovation workshop 2
Purpose	This activity is designed for workshop participants, now lab members, to explore and discuss localised social economy solutions, ultimately leading to a democratic selection of specific social economy initiatives.
Task / Task Leader	T3.3 / MedINA
Data	User-innovation workshop 2 data
Data collection/generation process	Workshop facilitators will document the minutes of the workshop and take photos of participants in action.
Data origin	The documentation will include records of participants' attendance, discussions, and decisions made during the workshop.

Storage format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • docx and .pdf for the minutes of the workshop • .jpeg for the images of participants in action
Expected data size	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less than 25 MB (up to 3 MB per pilot area) • Less than 700 MB (up to 100 MB per pilot area)
Other useful information	To safeguard participants' privacy, real names will be substituted with fictitious ones. Additionally, upon request, the faces of participants in images may be blurred.

Activity 7	Sustaining the Smart Village labs
Purpose	Local sustainability workshops in each lab will be deployed with key stakeholder participants to co-create a roadmap and Memorandum of collaboration to sustain the labs after the end of the project.
Task / Task Leader	T3.4 / Q-PLAN
Data	Sustainability workshops' results
Data collection/generation process	Labs' local sustainability workshops
Data origin	participants in local workshops (key stakeholders)
Storage format	.docx, .pdf, .xlsx
Expected data size	200 MB
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 8	Identification of key stakeholder participants for the local sustainability workshops
Purpose	Identify key stakeholder participants, local as well as stakeholders from 2 other rural areas with similar characteristics, who will be invited to participate in the local sustainability workshops in the pilot areas.
Task / Task Leader	T3.4 / Q-PLAN
Data	Data on local sustainability workshops participants
Data collection/generation process	Consortium partners' networks, online search of experts
Data origin	Consortium partners, web sources
Storage format	.xlsx
Expected data size	50 MB
Other useful information	N/A

2.2.4 WP4 Data collection/generation activities

Activity 1	Development of service programmes
Purpose	Training programmes (MOOCs)
Task / Task Leader	4.1 / KOC
Data	The findings of WP1 (i.e., needs and challenges of groups), WP2 (i.e., SE and service delivery challenges), and T3.2 (i.e., local needs under the labs)
Data collection/generation process	Needs Assessment and Planning, Curriculum Design, Content Creation, Active Learning Techniques, Technology Integration, Quality Assurance, Engagement Strategies, Post-Course Evaluation and Iteration
Data origin	WP1 and WP2 and T3.2
Storage format	MOOCs are stored in various formats to suit the diverse content types and platform requirements. Video content is typically saved as MP4 for its compatibility and efficient compression, or WEBM for web optimization. Text materials are commonly provided as PDFs for downloads, DOCX/TXT for editable or basic text, and HTML for in-platform interactive reading. Interactive elements are often created using H5P, a popular format for quizzes and simulations, while presentations may be stored in PPTX, KEY, or converted to SCORM/XAPI packages for use in Learning Management Systems (LMS).

	Audio content is usually in MP3 format for its compact size, or WAV for higher quality. Images are saved as PNG, JPG, or SVG, depending on the visual needs. For courses involving coding or datasets, ZIP files or Git repositories are common. Metadata and tracking data are often managed in CSV or JSON formats. Entire courses may be packaged in IMS Common Cartridge or zipped archives for interoperability or ease of transfer between platforms.
Expected data size	Typical MOOC Size <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small Course (4–6 Weeks): ~1–5 GB • Medium Course (8–10 Weeks): ~5–15 GB • Large Course (12+ Weeks): ~15–30 GB
Other useful information	Storage and Hosting Considerations: MOOC platforms (e.g., Coursera, edX) optimise file sizes and use cloud storage for scalability. Learners typically don't download the entire MOOC but access content through streaming or downloads of specific materials, further minimizing required storage on individual devices.

Activity 2	Needs Assessment of lab participants
Purpose	Distribute structured questionnaires to lab participants to gather quantitative data on their specific needs, ambitions, objectives, and challenges. This will help in identifying common themes and areas requiring targeted support.
Task / Task Leader	T4.2 / PEDAL
Data	Needs assessment of lab participants
Data collection/generation process	Questionnaires
Data origin	Stakeholders, lab participants
Storage format	.docx, .pdf
Expected data size	Less than 500 MB
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 3	Field Visits and Case Studies
Purpose	Document observations and insights from visits to successful social economy initiatives. Analysing these cases can provide valuable lessons and best practices that participants can adapt to their projects.
Task / Task Leader	T4.2 / PEDAL
Data	Field Visits and Case Studies
Data collection/generation process	Observational fieldwork
Data origin	Stakeholders, lab participants
Storage format	.docx, .pdf, .jpeg
Expected data size	Less than 2 GB
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 4	Co-Design Sessions
Purpose	Facilitate interactive sessions where participants, experts, and stakeholders collaboratively develop prototypes and solutions. This participatory approach ensures that the solutions are tailored to user needs and are practical for implementation.
Task / Task Leader	T4.2 / PEDAL
Data	Co-Design Sessions
Data collection/generation process	Note-Taking, Photographic Documentation, Surveys and Questionnaires, Post-Session Interviews
Data origin	Stakeholders, lab participants
Storage format	.docx, .pdf, .jpeg
Expected data size	Less than 1 GB
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 5	Events
Purpose	A two-day cross-territorial networking event will be organised, bringing together participants from all pilot regions for knowledge exchange. This event will complement other occasional gatherings, such as field visits to successful cases and sessions with social entrepreneurs and service providers, to provide comprehensive support and inspiration for participants.
Task / Task Leader	T4.2 / PEDAL
Data	Events information
Data collection/generation process	Note-Taking, Photographic Documentation, Surveys and Questionnaires, Post-Session Interviews
Data origin	Stakeholders, lab participants
Storage format	.docx, .pdf, web links
Expected data size	Between 1-5 GB
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 6	Pilot and scale up demonstration report
Purpose	Pilot and scale up demonstration report – the report will present the immediate operational interventions and outcomes from the 7 pilot cases
Task / Task Leader	T4.3 / WHEEL
Data	Pilot participants verbal feedback and observations
Data collection/generation process	On the ground observations by pilot partners, verbal feedback from pilot participants
Data origin	Informally interviewing and observing pilot stakeholders in each pilot area
Storage format	.docx, .pdf
Expected data size	Less than 1 GB
Other useful information	More formal feedback will be collected by WR in Task 4.4. The data gathered in Task 4.3 will be more informal and observational.

Activity 7	Quantitative data collection for evaluation of Smart Village Labs' impact
Purpose	The quantitative data collection activities are part of the monitoring and evaluation framework of the project, and aim to capture, measure and demonstrate the short-term impact of the pilot innovation activities that take place under the Smart Village Labs.
Task / Task Leader	T4.4 / WR
Data	Quantitative dataset on Smart Village Labs' impact
Data collection/generation process	Various quantitative instruments (depending on each pilot context): e.g., digital quizzes, online survey, on-site survey.
Data origin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Receivers of capacity-building activities (T4.1) • Initiators of SE-based projects (T4.2) • End-users of small-scale pilot projects (T4.3)
Storage format	.docx, .xlsx
Expected data size	No more than 1 GB
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 8	Qualitative data collection for evaluation of Smart Village Labs' impact
Purpose	The qualitative data collection activities are a complementary component to the quantitative data collection and whose main aim is to explain the quantitative results whenever and if needed (e.g., strong differences, poor progress).
Task / Task Leader	T4.4 / WR
Data	Qualitative dataset on Smart Village Labs' impact
Data collection/generation process	Various qualitative instruments (depending on each pilot context): e.g., explanatory face-to-face interviews)
Data origin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Receivers of capacity-building activities (T4.1)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initiators of SE-based projects (T4.2) • End-users of small-scale pilot projects (T4.3)
Storage format	.docx, .xlsx
Expected data size	No more than 1 GB
Other useful information	N/A

2.2.5 WP5 Data collection/generation activities

Activity 1	Network of Interest Stakeholder Engagement
Purpose	Establish a network to connect and engage stakeholders interested in rural development, social inclusion, and Smart Village initiatives.
Task / Task Leader	T5.1 / ERDN
Data	Stakeholder Contact and Profile Information
Data collection/generation process	Stakeholder interviews, surveys, and desk research to identify key actors across sectors (public, private, non-profit)
Data origin	Direct input from stakeholders, organisational websites, and public profiles.
Storage format	.xlsx, .docx, .csv
Expected data size	Less than 1 GB
Other useful information	Data includes names, affiliations, areas of interest, and roles in rural development projects.

Activity 2	Network Interaction Records
Purpose	Document stakeholder meetings, workshops, and collaborative sessions to understand network dynamics.
Task / Task Leader	T5.1 / ERDN
Data	Network Interaction Logs
Data collection/generation process	Documentation from meeting minutes, online platform interactions, and feedback forms from participants.
Data origin	Meeting minutes, logs of online interactions, participant feedback.
Storage format	.pdf, .docx
Expected data size	Less than 500 MB
Other useful information	Captures common areas of interest and collaborative outcomes for future reference.

Activity 3	Creation of the Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard
Purpose	To guide policymakers in identifying optimal service delivery and social economy solutions tailored to rural contexts while providing high-level policy guidelines. The activity integrates data from the territorial typology (T1.5), the Services and Social Economy Atlas (T2.4), and policy recommendations (T5.1) to develop a user-friendly dashboard for supporting informed rural policy-making and governance.
Task / Task Leader	T5.2 / SEERC
Data	Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard Dataset
Data collection/generation process	Integration of results from prior tasks (T1.5, T2.4, T5.1) into a unified dashboard
Data origin	Outputs from previous project tasks, including territorial typologies, atlases, and policy briefs
Storage format	Digital format (e.g., JSON, HTML for the dashboard), accompanying documentation in pdf
Expected data size	Less than 2 GB
Other useful information	The dashboard will include user-input functionalities and filters, allowing tailored recommendations. It will be hosted on the project's website and disseminated through the Network of Interest and partner channels.

Activity 4	Replication of INSPIRE activities in follower cases
Purpose	The activity aims to collect data that will support to transfer the INSPIRE concepts, research tools and methodological outcomes to additional cases in Europe.
Task / Task Leader	T5.3 / WR
Data	Data collected during the replication of INSPIRE activities in follower cases
Data collection/generation process	Notes and excel files retrieved from replication activities of the project (e.g., receiving input to develop the Guidebook, receiving input during the implementation of project results to follower cases).
Data origin	Representatives from follower cases
Storage format	.docx, .xlsx
Expected data size	1MB per .docx file / 5MB per .xlsx file
Other useful information	N/A

2.2.6 WP6 Data collection/generation activities

Activity 1	Monitoring and assessment of the website's dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement activities
Purpose	<p>The INSPIRE's website will be developed during the first months of the project (expected to be launched by M6, Mar 2025) and will be the main dissemination channel of the project, hosting the deliverables and links to the tools, providing information about the project, partners, and regions, as well as sharing news with a dedicated section and a newsletter. Two sets of data will be collected within this category:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visitors' statistics (anonymised data), through Google Analytics; • Newsletter subscribers, through MailChimp. <p>This type of information will be mostly used for reporting purposes. When people will visit the INSPIRE website, it will (via cookies - as in the case of every online website) automatically collect information about the visitor's device used for accessing the website (e.g., web browser, IP address, time zone). Additionally, information will be captured on how visitors interact with the website itself. We refer to this, automatically collected, information as "Device Information".</p> <p>To enhance the dissemination activities of the project, newsletter subscriptions are foreseen on the project's website. A subscription form hosted on the project's website will facilitate the collection of these data. Any interested stakeholder can voluntarily provide their contact details in a dedicated sign-up form, so as to receive the most up-to-date news and outcomes of the project. A newsletter will be sent to subscribers once per 6 months. These data will be collected so as interested stakeholders can be informed about INSPIRE. Along these lines, the data will be comprised of a list of subscribers along with their email address. A copy of this contact list will be stored on MailChimp's (http://mailchimp.com) server, which is used for e-mail campaigns and newsletters distribution. All personal information included in this contact list is used and protected according to MailChimp's Privacy Policy.</p>
Task / Task Leader	T6.1 / Q-PLAN
Data	Website analytics and Newsletter subscriptions
Data collection/generation process	Google Analytics (Visitors' statistics), MailChimp (Newsletter subscribers)
Data origin	INSPIRE website
Storage format	.docx, .xlsx, .csv, .ppt, .jpeg, .png, .pdf
Expected data size	200 MB
Other useful information	Data will be stored in spreadsheets (.xlsx) while the analysis of the results will be stored in a standard text document (.docx).

Activity 2	Monitoring and assessment of the social media dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement activities
Purpose	These data will be collected/generated through a periodic monitoring of the project's social media statistics (e.g., LinkedIn etc.) with a view to measuring and assessing the performance and results of the project's social media activity in terms of dissemination and communication. With that in mind, the data will be both qualitative as well as quantitative in nature addressing the metrics reached on each channel (e.g., number of followers, tweets impressions on Twitter, number of people reached through posts, etc.). Additionally, these data will be followed by an analysis of the results stemming from them and possible ways to improve the results so as to reach the project's targets.
Task / Task Leader	T6.1 / Q-PLAN
Data	Social Media statistics
Data collection/generation process	INSPIRE's social media analytics (TBD)
Data origin	INSPIRE's social media
Storage format	.docx, .xlsx, .csv, .ppt, .jpeg, .png, .pdf, web links
Expected data size	100 MB
Other useful information	The data will be stored in a spreadsheet (.xlsx) while at the same time the analysis of the results will be stored in a standard text document (.docx).

Activity 3	Monitoring and assessment of dissemination and communication activities and events
Purpose	These data will be collected through the periodic monitoring of the project's miscellaneous dissemination activities such as publications in relevant journals, posts in blogs, the different events (e.g., trainings, project workshops, interviews, INSPIRE EU-wide Final Conference in M36, physical and virtual events, etc. organised by INSPIRE, either alone or jointly with other projects or initiatives, consisting of the participants' lists that will enclose demographic information about the participants), the participation of INSPIRE partners in relevant third party events in order to reach out and engage stakeholders (thus collecting general information about the events attended and their outreach, etc. The data will consist of a spreadsheet designed to keep track of any kind of communication and dissemination activity, including, but not limited to, press releases, social media posts, website articles, interviews, events (conferences, meetings, workshops, etc.), other publications, e-mails, presentations, informal discussions, seminars, etc. The purpose of collecting these data is to assess the outreach and efficiency of the dissemination activities during the implementation of the project.
Task / Task Leader	T6.1 / Q-PLAN
Data	Data collected from dissemination and communication activities and events
Data collection/generation process	INSPIRE partners' input in the dissemination and communication reporting file (see other useful information)
Data origin	INSPIRE partners, web sources
Storage format	.docx, .xlsx, .csv, .jpeg, .png, .pdf, web links
Expected data size	Less than 300 MB
Other useful information	A file will be shared with all partners to log the activities they performed. The file will also be provided online so that the partners can directly update their input.

Activity 4	Project Synergies Identification and Engagement
Purpose	To identify and establish synergies with other projects in related areas (e.g., rural development, social inclusion, Smart Villages) to enhance collaboration, knowledge exchange, and dissemination impact.
Task / Task Leader	T6.2 / ERDN

Data	Project Synergies Database
Data collection/generation process	Desk research, literature review, and semi-structured interviews with partners and representatives from identified projects.
Data origin	Public project databases, project websites, and direct input from partners and project representatives.
Storage format	.xlsx, .docx, .pdf
Expected data size	Less than 500 MB
Other useful information	The database will include project names, objectives, key contacts, areas of overlap with the INSPIRE project, and potential collaboration opportunities. This information will be used to create a network of projects for ongoing synergy and joint dissemination activities.

2.2.7 WP7 Data collection/generation activities

Activity 1	Data generated through management and coordination actions
Purpose	The aim of WP7 data collection activities is to enable sound management and coordination of the project.
Task / Task Leader	T7.1, T7.2, T7.3, T7.4 / WR
Data	Names and e-mails of the INSPIRE consortium and financial information for companies, such as bank accounts.
Data collection/generation process	Data created from management and coordination activities: e.g., creation of consortium mailing lists, gathering of financial information and other type of data necessary for the coordination's activities.
Data origin	The data will origin from management and coordination activities and will be collected from consortium partners directly.
Storage format	.docx, .xlsx
Expected data size	500KB per .docx and 5MB per .xlsx
Other useful information	N/A

3. FAIR data

The [Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020](#) of the Commission highlight the importance of making the data produced by projects funded under Horizon 2020 **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable as well as Reusable (FAIR)**, with a view to ensuring its sound management. This means using standards and metadata to make data discoverable, specifying data sharing procedures and which data will be open, allowing data exchange via open repositories as well as facilitating the reusability of the data. The following sections of the DMP lay out the methodology followed in the framework of INSPIRE with respect to making data findable, accessible, and interoperable as well as ensuring their preservation and open access, with a view to increasing its re-use.

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Data discoverability and identification mechanisms

INSPIRE attributes special emphasis in enhancing the discoverability of the data collected/generated during its activities. To this end, the project follows a metadata-driven approach to increase the searchability of the data, while also facilitating its understanding and re-use. Metadata is defined as “data about data” or “information about information”⁴. It is usually structured textual information that describes something about the creation, content, or context of a digital resource – be it a single file, part of a single file, or a collection of many files. Metadata is the glue which links information and data across the world wide web. It is the tool that helps people to discover, manage, describe, preserve, and build relationships with and between digital resources⁵. Three distinct types of metadata exist⁶, as presented below:

- **Descriptive metadata** used to identify and describe collections and related information resources. Descriptive metadata at the local level helps with searching and retrieving. In an online environment, descriptive metadata helps to discover resources. Most of the times includes information such as the title, author, date, description, identifier, etc.
- **Administrative metadata** used to facilitate the management of information resources. It is helpful for both short-term and long-term management and processing of data. This is information that will not usually be relevant to the public but will be essential for staff to manage collections internally. Such metadata may be location information, acquisition information, etc.
- **Structural metadata** enables navigation and presentation of electronic resources. It documents how the components of an item are organised. Examples of structural metadata could be the way in which pages are ordered to form chapters of a book, a photograph that is included in a manuscript or a scrapbook or the .jpeg and .tiff files that were created from the original photograph negative, linked together.

⁴ Huxley, L., & Jacobs, N. (2004). *Online information services in the Social Sciences*. Oxford: Chandos.

⁵ Foulonneau, M., & Riley, J. (2008). *Metadata for digital resources: Implementation, systems design and interoperability*. Oxford: Chandos.

⁶ Caplan, P. (2003). *Metadata fundamentals for all librarians*. Chicago: American Library Association.

Data produced/used under the activities of INSPIRE's discoverable with metadata suitable to its content and format. The project employs metadata standards to produce rich and consistent metadata to support the long-term discovery, use and integrity of its data (see Subsection 3.1.5 for more details on the metadata standards adopted by INSPIRE). **Furthermore, all research outputs under public status that will be produced in the framework of the project (deliverables, datasets, policy briefs, etc.) will be uploaded and deposited to the INSPIRE project website and open access platforms, such as Zenodo and Research Gate.** In this way, we attempt to further increase data discoverability, under the framework of inspire. The datasets uploaded to the website of the project will utilise well-tailored identification mechanisms, in the form of standard naming conventions that will safeguard their consistency and make them easily locatable for project partners within the framework of the project. The following subsection provides further details in this respect.

Zenodo⁷ has been identified as an option to enable open access to the project's open data, free of charge. In fact, Zenodo builds and operates a simple service that enables researchers, scientists, EU projects, and institutions to share and showcase research results (including data and publications) that are not part of the existing institutional or subject-based repositories of the research communities. It accepts any file format, promotes peer-reviewed openly accessible research, allows the creation of own collections, and is available free of charge both for INSPIRE to upload and share data and other stakeholders to explore, download and re-use this data.

Moreover, by employing this data repository, the **data produced throughout the project is locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism.** INSPIRE will be able to assign globally resolvable **Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)** on any data uploaded to Zenodo. An identifier is a unique identification code applied to a dataset to be unambiguously referenced⁸. For example, a catalogue number is an identifier for a specimen, and an ISBN code is an identifier for a particular book. PIDs are maintainable identifiers that allow for permanent reference to a digital object. In other words, PIDs are a way of giving digital resources, such as documents, images and data records, a unique and persistent reference number.

Zenodo registers **Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs)** for all submitted data through [DataCite](https://datacite.org/), the leading global non-profit organisation that provides PIDs (and specifically DOIs) for research data. At the same time, it preserves these submissions using the safe and trusted foundation of CERN's data centre, alongside the biggest scientific dataset in the world, the LHC's 100PB Big Data store⁹. This means that the data preserved in Zenodo will be accessible for years to come, and the DOIs will function as perpetual links to the resources. DOIs remain valuable since they are future-proofed against Uniform Resource Locator (URL) or even protocol changes, through resolvers (such as [DOI](https://doi.org/)). **Results that are not uploaded to Zenodo or another open access platform, such as dissemination material produced during the life-span of the project, will be deposited in a searchable resource (i.e., the website of the project) and utilise well-tailored identification mechanisms** in the form of standard naming conventions. This will safeguard their consistency and

⁷ See [www.Zenodo.org](https://www.zenodo.org)

⁸ Tonkin, E. Persistent identifiers: considering the options (2008), Ariadne Issue 56.

⁹ Retrieved from: <https://www.software.ac.uk/tags/Zenodo>

make them **easily locatable** for project partners. The following subsection provides further details in this respect.

3.1.2 Naming conventions

Data searchability can be greatly enhanced following a consistent set of naming conventions. In this align, INSPIRE creates consistent data file names that provide clues to their content, status, and versioning, while also increasing their discoverability. In doing so, project partners as well as interested stakeholders can easily identify a file as well as classify and sort them. According to the UK Data Archive ([UK Data Service](#)), a best practice in naming convention is to create brief yet meaningful names for data files, that facilitate classification. The naming convention should **avoid the use of special characters** (such as & or !), whereas the use of underscores is endorsed, to separate elements in the data file name and make them understandable. At the same time, **versioning should be a part of a naming convention to clearly identify the changes and edits in a file.**

INSPIRE uses a **standard naming convention that integrates versioning and considers the possibility of creating multiple datasets** during an activity that entails data collection/generation. Indeed, INSPIRE's naming convention contemplates this issue and addresses it by employing a unique element that captures the number of datasets that are produced under the same activity.

In particular, the **naming convention employed by the project is described below.**

INSPIRE_ [Name of Study] _ [Number of the dataset] _ [Issue Date] _ [Version number]

- **INSPIRE:** The name of the project.
- **Name of Study:** A short version of the name of the activity for which the dataset is created.
- **Number of the dataset:** An indication of the number assigned to the dataset.
- **Issue Date:** The date on which the latest version of the dataset was modified (YYYY.MM.DD.).
- **Version number:** The versioning number of a dataset.

An **indicative example** showcasing the naming structure applied in the project's context is given below:

INSPIRE_Forecast of trends and drivers of social exclusion in rural areas
_Dataset2_2025.30.04_v1 – *The second dataset generated within the implementation of WP1 in the framework of T1.2. This is the first version of the dataset that was last modified on the 30th of April 2025 (30/04/2025).*

3.1.3 Search keywords

The project's data will be provided with easy-to-use search keywords with a view to optimise its re-use by interested stakeholders during its entire lifetime. With that in mind, the metadata standards employed by INSPIRE provide opportunities for tagging the data collected/generated and its content with keywords. In general, keywords are a subset of metadata and include words and phrases used to name data. In the context of INSPIRE, keywords are used to add valuable information to the data collected/generated as well as to facilitate the description and interpretation of its content and value. Along these lines, the project's strategy on keywords is underpinned by the following principles:

- The who, the what, the when, the where, and the why should be covered.
- Consistency among the different keyword tags needs to be ensured.

- Relevant, understandable, and clear keywording ought to be sought.

In general, the keywords will comprise terms related to: social inclusion, rural development, vulnerable groups, social entrepreneurship and social economy, social services, governance frameworks, smart village. The keywords will accurately reflect the content of the datasets and avoid words used only once or twice within them.

3.1.4 Versioning

Versioning of information makes a revision of datasets uniquely identifiable and can be used to determine whether and how data changed over time and to define specifically which version the creators/editors are working with. Moreover, effective data versioning enables understanding if a newer version of a dataset is available and which are the changes between the different versions allowing for comparisons and preventing confusion. In this context, **a clear version number indicator is used in the naming convention** of every data file produced during INSPIRE to facilitate the identification of different versions. In the case of data uploaded on Zenodo, the version control of our shared data is managed through Zenodo repository.

3.1.5 Standards for metadata creation

Searchability and discoverability of the collected/generated dataset, in the context of INSPIRE, is ensured through utilisation of rich metadata standards. This process results in effective searching, improved digital curation and easy sharing of the data while the standards applied enable the integration of metadata from a variety of sources into other technical systems.

Project **data will be annotated with open and machine-readable metadata** following the **Dublin Core Metadata standard**. The Dublin Core Metadata element set (certified with the ISO Standard 15836) is a standard which can be easily understood and implemented and as such, is one of the best-known metadata standards. It was originally developed as a core set of elements for describing the content of websites and enabling their search and retrieval. The Dublin Core metadata standard is a simple yet effective set for creating rich metadata that will describe a wide range of resources. The fifteen element "Dublin Core" described in this standard is part of a larger set of metadata vocabularies and technical specifications maintained by the [Dublin Core Metadata Initiative \(DCMI\)](#). The full set of vocabularies also includes sets of resource classes, vocabulary encoding schemes, and syntax encoding schemes. **An online metadata generator will be used** to produce the different metadata elements required ([dublincoregenerator.com](#)).

3.2 Making data openly accessible

3.2.1 Openly available and closed data

INSPIRE is committed to the Open Data principles to “make the data collected/generated by selected projects openly available with as few restrictions as possible, while at the same time protecting sensitive data from inappropriate access”. The project adopts the good practice encouraged by the Open Data principles, namely that of **making data as open as possible and as closed, as necessary**. This calls for project partners to disseminate the project’s data that have the potential to offer long-term value to external stakeholders and do not harm the confidentiality and privacy of the

stakeholders that contributed to the collection/generation of this data, with a view to maximising the beneficial impact of INSPIRE.

Only anonymised and aggregated data will be made open to ensure that data subjects cannot be identified in any reports, publications and/or datasets resulting from the project. The project partner serving as the data controller in each case will undertake all the necessary anonymisation procedures to anonymise the data in such a way that the data subject is no longer identifiable (more details on data management responsibilities are provided in *Section 4.2*).

To this end, it is important to keep in mind that during the process of data anonymisation, data identifiers need to be removed, generalised, aggregated, or distorted. Moreover, anonymisation is different than pseudonymisation, which falls under a distinct category in the GDPR - **anonymisation theoretically destroys any way of identifying the data subject, while pseudonymisation allows for the data subject to be re-identified with additional information**. Along these lines, the table below provides a list of good practices for the anonymisation of quantitative and qualitative data derived from the tour guide on data management of the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA).

Type of data	Good practices
Quantitative data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Removing or aggregate variables or reduce the precision or detailed textual meaning of a variable. ● Aggregate or reduce the precision of a variable such as age or place of residence. Generally, report the lowest level of geo-referencing that will not potentially breach respondent confidentiality (accounting also the fact that the place of residence will match the location of the specific community selected by the pilot partner). ● Generalise the meaning of a detailed text variable by replacing potentially disclosive free-text responses with more general text. ● Restrict the upper or lower ranges of a continuous variable to hide outliers if the values for certain individuals are unusual or atypical within the wider group researched.
Qualitative data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Use pseudonyms or generic descriptors to edit identifying information, rather than blanking-out that information. ● Plan anonymisation at the time of transcription or initial write-up, (longitudinal studies may be an exception if relationships between waves of interviews need special attention for harmonised editing). ● Use pseudonyms or replacements that are consistent within the research team and throughout the project. For example, using the same pseudonyms in publications and follow-up research. ● Use 'search and replace' techniques carefully so that unintended changes are not made, and misspelt words are not missed. ● Identify replacements in text clearly, for example with [brackets] or using XML tags such as <seg>word to be anonymised</seg>.

- Create an anonymisation log (also known as a de-anonymisation key) of all replacements, aggregations or removals made and store such a log securely and separately from the anonymised data files.

Source: Tour guide on data management of the CESSDA¹⁰.

3.2.2 Methods, software tools and documentation to access the data

INSPIRE emphasises the accessibility of the data collected/generated during the project. With that in mind, no specialised method, software tool and/or documentation is expected to be needed at the moment, in order to access the data. Stakeholders will have the ability to access the data by simply using their web browser (e.g., Mozilla, Google Chrome, Internet Explorer, Safari, etc.) through their computers (either desktop or laptop), smart phones and/or tablets. Moreover, since the data will be available in open formats, we will be ensuring that they can appropriately be read by a range of different software that are widely and freely accessible to all potential users of the data.

Closed data will only be accessed by authorised project partners through the usage of a cloud storage (Google Drive) or online file sharing systems in accordance with the data security principles (*section 4*). Again, no specialised method, software tool and/or documentation is needed to this end.

3.2.3 Data, metadata, code and documentation repositories

INSPIRE's open data along with their linking metadata as well as any relevant code and documentation (if applicable) required to access this data, will be deposited to, and securely stored by INSPIRE website. INSPIRE's open data along with their linking metadata as well as any relevant code and documentation (if applicable) required to access this data, will be deposited to and securely stored by Zenodo or another open access platform, and available on the project webpage. In parallel, project's data that will not be openly available for sharing will be deposited, together with their accompanying metadata, code, and documentation (if necessary), to the cloud web storage service employed by the project.

3.3 Making data interoperable

Data interoperability refers to the ability of systems and services that create, exchange, and use data to have clear, shared expectations for the contents, context and meaning of that data¹¹. INSPIRE has adopted in its data management methodology the use of metadata vocabularies, standards and methods that will increase the interoperability of the data collected/generated through its activities.

More specifically, **the interoperability of the data that will not be publicly shared will be facilitated using the Dublin Core Metadata standard**. This standard is a small “metadata element set” which accounts for issues that must be resolved in order to ensure that data meet traditional standards for quality and consistency, while remaining broadly interoperable with other data sources

¹⁰ Retrieved from: <https://www.cessda.eu/Research-Infrastructure/Training/Expert-Tour-Guide-on-Data-Management/5.-Protect/Anonymisation>.

¹¹ L. Steele & T. Orrell (2017). The frontiers of data interoperability for sustainable development. Publish What You Fund and Development Initiatives.

in the linked data environment. The fifteen elements of the standard provide a vocabulary of concepts with natural-language definitions (e.g., title, creator, author, etc.) that are instantly converted into open machine-readable formats (such as XML, HTML, etc.), enabling machine-processability. Each element is optional and may be repeated, while the standard itself offers existing ways for refining them, encouraging the use of encoding and vocabulary schemes. The vocabulary of the Dublin Core Metadata standard is presented by Table 3¹²:

Table 3. Dublin Core Metadata standard vocabulary

No.	Element	Element definition
1	Title	A name given to the resource.
2	Creator	An entity primarily responsible for making the content of the resource.
3	Subject	The topic of the content of the resource.
4	Description	An account of the content of the resource.
5	Publisher	An entity responsible for making the resource available.
6	Contributor	An entity responsible for making contributions to the content of the resource.
7	Date	A date associated with an event in the life cycle of the resource
8	Type	The nature or genre of the content of the resource.
9	Format	The physical or digital manifestation of the resource.
10	Identifier	An unambiguous reference to the resource within a given context.
11	Source	A reference to a resource from which the present resource is derived.
12	Language	A language of the intellectual content of the resource.
13	Relation	A reference to a related resource.
14	Coverage	The extent or scope of the content of the resource.
15	Rights	Information about rights held in and over the resource.

3.4 Making data re-useable

3.4.1 Availability for re-use

Data re-usability constitutes a key element of INSPIRE FAIR data management methodology. Making data available for re-use ensures interested stakeholders, other than project partners, can benefit from this data, contributing towards maximising the impact of the project. Rich metadata created based on metadata standards that enable proper detection as well as appropriate licensing schemes facilitate the re-use of INSPIRE’s open data, allowing them to find valuable utility. In principle, it is expected that open data will become available for re-use no later than 120 days after the end of its processing in the framework of the project (i.e., collection, anonymisation, aggregation, etc.) to ensure that any additional data management activities required to this end do not compete with the timely delivery of the project’s planned outputs.

¹² Sugimoto, S., Baker, T., & Weibel, S. L. (2002). Dublin Core: Process and Principles. Lecture Notes in Computer Science Digital Libraries: People, Knowledge, and Technology, 25-35.

3.4.2 Data quality assurance processes

Quality Assurance (QA) and Quality Control (QC) activities are an integral part of INSPIRE's data management methodology and are implemented prior to the publication of any data to INSPIRE website, safeguarding the transparency, consistency, comparability, completeness, and accuracy of the data.

QA is a planned system of review procedures conducted outside the framework of developing a dataset, by personnel not directly involved in the dataset development process¹³. In the context of INSPIRE, it takes the form of peer-reviews of methods and/or data summaries to assess the quality of the dataset and identify any need for improvement, ensures that the dataset correctly incorporates the scientific knowledge and data generated.

QC is defined as a system of checks to assess and maintain the quality of the dataset being compiled¹⁴. The relevant procedures of INSPIRE are designed to provide routine technical checks as they measure and control data consistency, integrity, correctness, and completeness as well as identify and address errors and omissions. In this context, QC checks cover everything from data acquisition and handling, application of approved procedures and methods, and documentation. Some of the general quality checks undertaken in the framework of the project include checking (i) for transcription errors in data input (ii) that scale measures are within the range of acceptable values and (iii) whether proper naming conversions are used.

3.5 Availability and accessibility of data

The following tables presents the data collected/generated during the project that will be made openly available. In case certain data cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), a justification for that choice is provided.

It is important to note that **all personal data collected/generated will be considered as closed data prior to their anonymisation and aggregation** to safeguard the confidentiality of the data subjects.

Public access to the open data will be made possible through an open-access platform, such as the Zenodo repository, and linked to the INSPIRE project website.

At the same time, closed data are intended to be stored and shared only amongst authorised members of the consortium through cloud storage and file sharing providers which constitute structures that maintain and manage data and make this data accessible over the internet. Such systems need to guarantee data security (*Section 4*). In this context, the INSPIRE Google Drive repository offers secure and reserved access only to project partners and serves as an online directory for file storing and exchange within the INSPIRE consortium. As PC of INSPIRE, White Research is responsible for setting up and managing the Google Driver repository of the project. WR uses paid Google licences and therefore offers to the project sufficient drive security requirements

¹³ 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories, Vol. 1 General Guidance and Reporting, CHAPTER 6 Quality Assurance / Quality Control and Verification.

¹⁴ 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories, Vol. 1 General Guidance and Reporting, CHAPTER 6 Quality Assurance / Quality Control and Verification.

compared to free drives, rendering the Google Drive of INSPIRE a safe internal environment. More specific provisions will be defined in the updated version of this DMP for any research related sensitive data. The following tables present the ways with which data will be made accessible in the context of INSPIRE.

3.5.1 WP1 Data collection/generation activities

Activity 1	Systematic review on social exclusion in rural areas
Task	T1.1 / SEERC
Data	Social Exclusion in Rural Areas - Measurement Framework
Availability	Open
Notes on Availability	To be available through the INSPIRE website after validation and approval of the framework.
Accessible through	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> INSPIRE website Zenodo repository
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	March 2025 (After approval of Deliverable D1.1)
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Universities, Horizon Europe beneficiaries, policymakers, and researchers in social inclusion may use this data to refine definitions, measurement tools, and indicators related to social exclusion in rural areas.
Other useful information	The dataset will include a comprehensive list of indicators and a validated methodological framework, making it a reference point for future research and policymaking.

Activity 2	Forecast of trends and drivers of social exclusion in rural areas
Task	T1.2 / Q-PLAN
Data	Delphi questionnaire results on social exclusion forecast
Availability	Open
Notes on Availability	To be available through D1.2 and Zenodo. Only anonymised and aggregated data will be open to ensure that data subjects cannot be identified.
Accessible through	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> INSPIRE website Zenodo repository
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	March 2026 (After approval of the respective deliverable or after publication of results as a paper in a scientific journal)
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Rural areas in Europe and worldwide, Universities worldwide, Horizon Europe beneficiaries, and stakeholders in other social economy initiatives may use this data to enrich their literature review and/or adopt best practices about social economy initiatives in rural areas.
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 3	Identification of expert participants for the Delphi exercise
Task	T1.2 / Q-PLAN
Data	Data on Delphi exercise participants
Availability	To remain closed because they contain personal data. Available only to Q-PLAN and the EU Commission.
Notes on Availability	N/A
Accessible through	N/A
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	N/A
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	N/A
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 4	National survey on social exclusion
Task	T1.3 / RUG
Data	Social Exclusion Survey
Availability	Open
Notes on Availability	To be available through D1.2 and Zenodo
Accessible through	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> INSPIRE website Zenodo repository
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	March 2026 (After approval of the respective deliverable or after publication of results as a paper in a scientific journal)
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Rural areas in Europe and worldwide, Universities worldwide, Horizon Europe beneficiaries, and stakeholders in other social economy initiatives may use this data to enrich their literature review and/or adopt best practices about social economy initiatives in rural areas.
Other useful information	All information that can potentially lead to identification of survey participant will be removed from the publicly available dataset (.csv).

Activity 5	National Interviews with QH stakeholders
Task	T1.3 / RUG
Data	Quadruple Helix Stakeholder Interviews
Availability	Open
Notes on Availability	To be available through D1.2 and Zenodo
Accessible through	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> INSPIRE website Zenodo repository
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	March 2026 (After approval of the respective deliverable or after publication of results as a paper in a scientific journal)
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Rural areas in Europe and worldwide, Universities worldwide, Horizon Europe beneficiaries, and stakeholders in other social economy initiatives may use this data to enrich their literature review and/or adopt best practices about social economy initiatives in rural areas.
Other useful information	All information that can potentially lead to identification of survey participants will be removed from the publicly available datasets (e.g., .docx, audio files).

Activity 6	Observational fieldwork in pilot areas
Task	T1.4 / UB
Data	Data from observational fieldwork in pilot areas
Availability	Open
Notes on Availability	To be available through project repository
Accessible through	INSPIRE internal project repository
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	November 2025 (After approval of the respective deliverable)
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Universities worldwide, Horizon Europe beneficiaries, and stakeholders in other social economy initiatives may use this data to get micro-level information on community and individual specificities to consider when adopting best practices about social economy initiatives in rural areas.
Other useful information	Only data that can be anonymised and shared – to be decided upon data collection

Activity 7	CATI surveys for micro-level data
Task	T1.4 / UB
Data	CATI surveys
Availability	Open
Notes on Availability	To be available through project repository
Accessible through	INSPIRE internal project repository

Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	November 2025 (After approval of the respective deliverable)
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Universities worldwide, Horizon Europe beneficiaries, and stakeholders in other social economy initiatives may use this data to get micro-level information on community and individual specificities to consider when adopting best practices about social economy initiatives in rural areas.
Other useful information	30 answers x 7 pilots = 210 answers in total

Activity 8	Paper-based surveys for micro-level data
Task	T1.4 / UB
Data	Paper-based surveys
Availability	Open
Notes on Availability	To be available through project repository
Accessible through	INSPIRE project internal repository
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	November 2025 (After approval of the respective deliverable)
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Universities worldwide, Horizon Europe beneficiaries, and stakeholders in other social economy initiatives may use this data to get micro-level information on community and individual specificities to consider when adopting best practices about social economy initiatives in rural areas.
Other useful information	20 answers x 7 pilots = 140 answers in total

Activity 9	Typology on social wellbeing, resilience and exclusion of European rural areas
Task	T1.5 / UB
Data	Typology of rural areas
Availability	Open
Notes on Availability	To be available through project website and Policy Dashboard
Accessible through	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> INSPIRE project website INSPIRE Policy Dashboard
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	November 2025 (After approval of the respective deliverable)
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Universities worldwide, Horizon Europe beneficiaries, and stakeholders in other social economy initiatives may use this typology when adopting best practices about social economy initiatives in rural areas.
Other useful information	N/A

3.5.2 WP2 Data collection/generation activities

Activity 1	Desk research
Task	Explore definitions and legal frameworks for social services in rural areas. Map 50+ services and initiatives supporting social inclusion
Data	INSPIRE Rural Services and Legal Framework Database
Availability	Open
Notes on Availability	To be available through the INSPIRE website and partners' webpages after the completion of desk research.
Accessible through	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> INSPIRE website Partners' webpages
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	February 2025 (post-desk research deliverable approval).
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Researchers, policymakers, and rural development practitioners can use the dataset to identify gaps in service provision and adapt legal frameworks to

	enhance social inclusion. Useful for EU policymakers, local governments, researchers, and NGOs interested in rural social inclusion services.
Other useful information	Includes metadata on services by region, sector, target population, and legal frameworks to support evidence-based policy. Data includes services by type, end-users, region, legal framework.

Activity 2	Semi-structured Interviews
Task	Collect qualitative insights on social inclusion policies, services, and challenges from stakeholders.
Data	INSPIRE stakeholder interview dataset
Availability	Closed
Notes on Availability	To remain closed to ensure the privacy of interview participants. Anonymised insights will be included in project reports and publications.
Accessible through	Summarised findings accessible via project deliverables and publications.
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	N/A
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Provides qualitative context for policymakers and researchers focusing on barriers to social inclusion in rural Europe.
Other useful information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Includes anonymised quotes and aggregated findings from regional and pilot area stakeholders. Insights to inform the "Atlas" and policy recommendations in the project deliverables.

Activity 3	Focus Groups
Task	Evaluate the effectiveness, strengths, and weaknesses of identified social inclusion services through qualitative discussions with end-users and providers.
Data	INSPIRE Focus Group Dataset
Availability	Closed
Notes on Availability	To remain closed to protect participant identities and sensitive discussions. Anonymised summaries will be made public.
Accessible through	Summary findings via INSPIRE deliverables and publications.
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	N/A
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Valuable for service providers, researchers, and policymakers to understand user perspectives and improve service delivery.
Other useful information	Insights to inform the "Atlas" and policy recommendations in the project deliverables.

Activity 4	Conceptual definitions and legal frameworks of social economy in the EU
Task	T2.2 / SEE
Data	Definitions and legal frameworks
Availability	Open
Notes on Availability	To be available online
Accessible through	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> INSPIRE website SEE webpage or Zenodo repository (TBD)
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	March 2025 (After approval of the respective deliverable)
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Researchers, policy makers and social economy stakeholders
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 5	Impact frameworks at global, EU and national level to evaluate social economy services
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Task	T2.2 / SEE
Data	Impact frameworks
Availability	Open
Notes on Availability	To be available online
Accessible through	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> INSPIRE website SEE webpage Zenodo repository (TBD)
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	March 2025 (After approval of the respective deliverable)
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Researchers, policy makers and social economy stakeholders
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 6	Digital Ethnography
Task	T2.3 / RUG
Data	Digital Ethnography
Availability	Closed
Notes on Availability	To remain closed because of risk of personal identification, disclosure of sensitive information on SMEs
Accessible through	Digital Ethnography
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	N/A
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	N/A
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 7	Microsimulation – Agent Based Modelling
Task	T2.3 / RUG
Data	Spatial microsimulation and agent based modelling
Availability	Open
Notes on Availability	To be available through INSPIRE website
Accessible through	INSPIRE website (reproducible spatial microsimulation code and ABM models)
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	July 2026 (6 months after submission of D2.3)
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Researchers, policy makers and social economy stakeholders
Other useful information	N/A

3.5.3 WP3 Data collection/generation activities

Activity 1	Pilot Area Environmental and Needs Assessment
Task	T3.1 / CZU
Data	Territorial profiles of pilot sites
Availability	Open
Notes on Availability	To be available through INSPIRE project website
Accessible through	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> INSPIRE website partners' webpages Zenodo repository
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	End of January 2026 (After approval of the deliverable 3.1)
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Universities worldwide, Horizon Europe beneficiaries, and stakeholders in other social economy initiatives may use this data to enrich their literature review and/or adopt best practices about social economy initiatives in rural areas.

Other useful information	N/A
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Activity 2	Targeted Community Engagement and Vulnerability Assessment
Task	T3.1 / CZU
Data	Territorial profiles of pilot sites
Availability	Open
Notes on Availability	To be available through INSPIRE project website
Accessible through	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> INSPIRE website partners' webpages Zenodo repository
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	End of January 2026 (After approval of the deliverable 3.1)
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Universities worldwide, Horizon Europe beneficiaries, and stakeholders in other social economy initiatives may use this data to enrich their literature review and/or adopt best practices about social economy initiatives in rural areas.
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 3	Local awareness raising campaigns in 7 pilot areas
Task	T3.2 / WR
Data	Analytics of local awareness raising campaigns (e.g., number of participants in local fairs, analytics of social media campaigns).
Availability	Closed
Notes on Availability	To remain closed because the D3.2 in which these analytics will be reported, is sensitive (SEN).
Accessible through	Part of results that do not contain personal or sensitive information may become available through INSPIRE website (e.g., press releases, website articles).
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	N/A
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Stakeholders from public sector or civil society who run initiatives on social engagement and participatory methods in rural areas and vulnerable populations.
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 4	Local co-creation workshops on Smart Village Labs in 7 pilot areas
Task	T3.2 /WR
Data	Analytics of local creation workshops on (e.g., number of participants in the workshop, video and photo evidence).
Availability	Closed
Notes on Availability	To remain closed because the D3.2 in which these analytics will be reported, is sensitive (SEN).
Accessible through	Part of results that do not contain personal or sensitive information may become available through INSPIRE website (e.g., press releases, website articles).
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	N/A
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Stakeholders from public sector or civil society who run initiatives on social engagement and participatory methods in rural areas and vulnerable populations.
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 5	User-innovation workshop 1
Task	T3.3 / MedINA
Data	User-innovation workshop 1 data
Availability	Open

Notes on Availability	Data for this task will be available through a dedicated record in Zenodo, including a permanent identifier in the form of a Digital Object Identifier (DOI).
Accessible through	Zenodo repository
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	July 2026, shortly after the approval of Deliverable D3.3
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Researchers, Horizon Europe consortiums working on related topics, service providers in rural areas, and practitioners in the social economy can use this data to enhance their work in studying and developing solutions that address local needs in rural communities.
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 6	User-innovation workshop 2
Task	T3.3 / MedINA
Data	User-innovation workshop 2 data
Availability	Open
Notes on Availability	Data for this task will be available through a dedicated record in Zenodo, including a permanent identifier in the form of a Digital Object Identifier (DOI).
Accessible through	Zenodo repository
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	July 2026, shortly after the approval of Deliverable D3.3
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Researchers, Horizon Europe consortiums working on related topics, service providers in rural areas, and practitioners in the social economy can use this data to enhance their work in studying and developing solutions that address local needs in rural communities, particularly concerning social economy initiatives.
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 7	Sustaining the Smart Village labs
Task	T3.4 / Q-PLAN
Data	Sustainability workshops' results
Availability	Open
Notes on Availability	To be available through D3.4
Accessible through	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> INSPIRE website Zenodo repository
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	October 2025 (After approval of the respective deliverable)
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Stakeholders in other social economy initiatives may use this data to adopt best practices about social economy initiatives in rural areas.
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 8	Identification of key stakeholder participants for the local sustainability workshops
Task	T3.4 / Q-PLAN
Data	Data on local sustainability workshops participants
Availability	Closed
Notes on Availability	To remain closed because they contain personal data. Available only to the INSPIRE consortium and the EU Commission.
Accessible through	N/A
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	N/A
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	N/A
Other useful information	N/A

3.5.4 WP4 Data collection/generation activities

Activity 1	Development of service programmes
Task	4.1 /KOC
Data	Training programmes (MOOCs)
Availability	Open
Notes on Availability	To be available through August 2026 (Month 22)
Accessible through	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> INSPIRE website partners' webpages Zenodo repository
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	August 2026 (After approval of the respective deliverable)
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Rural residents who face accessibility challenges to education will benefit from these digital courses. Universities worldwide, Horizon Europe beneficiaries, and stakeholders in other social economy initiatives may also use these online courses and/or adopt best practices about social economy initiatives in rural areas.
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 2	Needs Assessment of lab participants
Task	T4.2 / PEDAL
Data	Needs assessment of lab participants
Availability	Closed
Notes on Availability	To remain closed because of D4.2 dissemination level is Sensitive
Accessible through	INSPIRE internal repository
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	N/A
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	N/A
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 3	Field Visits and Case Studies
Task	T4.2 / PEDAL
Data	Field Visits and Case Studies
Availability	Open
Notes on Availability	To be available through WP6/T6.1
Accessible through	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> INSPIRE website Social Media channels partners' webpages
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	M22-M36
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Universities worldwide, Horizon Europe beneficiaries, and stakeholders in other social economy initiatives may use this data to enrich their literature review and/or adopt best practices about social economy initiatives in rural areas.
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 4	Co-Design Sessions
Task	T4.2 / PEDAL
Data	Co-Design Sessions
Availability	Closed
Notes on Availability	To remain closed because of D4.2 dissemination level is Sensitive
Accessible through	INSPIRE internal repository

Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	N/A
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	N/A
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 5	Events
Task	T4.2 / PEDAL
Data	Events information
Availability	Open
Notes on Availability	To be available through WP6/T6.1
Accessible through	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> INSPIRE website Social Media channels partners' webpages
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	M22-M36
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Universities worldwide, Horizon Europe beneficiaries, and stakeholders in other social economy initiatives may use this data to enrich their literature review and/or adopt best practices about social economy initiatives in rural areas.
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 6	Pilot and scale up demonstration report
Task	T4.3 / WHEEL
Data	Pilot participants feedback and observations
Availability	Open
Notes on Availability	To be available through INSPIRE project website (the report will be uploaded on the website)
Accessible through	INSPIRE website, partners' webpages
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	March 2027 (After approval of the respective deliverable)
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Stakeholders in other social economy initiatives may use this data to adopt best practices about social economy initiatives in rural areas.
Other useful information	This data collected by pilot partners will ultimately feature in the pilot report and pilot participants feedback will be anonymous.

Activity 7	Quantitative data collection for evaluation of Smart Village Labs' impact
Task	T4.4 / WR
Data	Quantitative dataset on Smart Village Labs' impact
Availability	Closed
Notes on Availability	To remain closed because the D4.4 in which these analytics will be reported, is sensitive (SEN).
Accessible through	Part of results that do not contain personal or sensitive information may become available through scientific publications that will be based on D4.4.
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	N/A
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Researchers and academics, civil society actors and civil servants/decision makers who work on policy interventions and evaluation in the field of social inclusion.
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 8	Qualitative data collection for evaluation of Smart Village Labs' impact
Task	T4.4 / WR
Data	Qualitative dataset on Smart Village Labs' impact

Availability	Closed
Notes on Availability	To remain closed because the D4.4 in which these analytics will be reported, is sensitive (SEN).
Accessible through	Part of results that do not contain personal or sensitive information may become available through scientific publications that will be based on D4.4.
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	N/A
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Researchers and academics, civil society actors and civil servants/decision makers who work on policy interventions and evaluation in the field of social inclusion.
Other useful information	N/A

3.5.5 WP5 Data collection/generation activities

Activity 1	Network of Interest Stakeholder Engagement
Task	T5.1 / ERDN
Data	Stakeholder Contact and Profile Information
Availability	Closed initially, open upon anonymisation.
Notes on Availability	Available on the INSPIRE website and Zenodo repository after stakeholder consent and anonymisation.
Accessible through	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> INSPIRE website Zenodo repository
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	After consent is given by engaged stakeholders
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Useful for Horizon Europe beneficiaries, social economy initiatives, and policymakers interested in rural inclusion practices.
Other useful information	Anonymisation ensures privacy while enabling valuable insights for policy development.

Activity 2	Network Interaction Records
Task	T5.1 / ERDN
Data	Network Interaction Logs
Availability	Closed initially, anonymised records open later.
Notes on Availability	Accessible through the INSPIRE website after review and anonymisation.
Accessible through	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> INSPIRE website Zenodo repository
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	Just after the activities starts
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Provides insights into network dynamics for other EU projects and initiatives related to social inclusion.
Other useful information	Anonymised data allows sharing without compromising stakeholder confidentiality.

Activity 3	Creation of the Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard
Task	T5.2 / SEERC
Data	Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard Dataset
Availability	
Notes on Availability	Open
Accessible through	To be available through the INSPIRE website after the finalisation and approval of the dashboard.
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> INSPIRE website Zenodo repository

Data utility (to external stakeholders)	October 2027 (After approval of Deliverable D5.2)
Other useful information	Policymakers, researchers, Horizon Europe beneficiaries, and rural development stakeholders may use this dashboard to design evidence-based policies, improve governance, and implement targeted social economy solutions.

Activity 4	Replication of INSPIRE activities in follower cases
Task	T5.3 / WR
Data	Data collected during the replication of INSPIRE activities in follower cases
Availability	Open
Notes on Availability	To be available through D5.3.
Accessible through	Accessible through: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Google Drive* • INSPIRE website
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	After the end of M36.
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Public agencies, civil society actors and civil servants/decision makers who work on social inclusion and governance frameworks in rural areas.
Other useful information	N/A

3.5.6 WP6 Data collection/generation activities

Activity 1	Monitoring and assessment of the website’s dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement activities
Task	T6.1 / Q-PLAN
Data	Website analytics and Newsletter subscriptions
Availability	Closed & Open
Notes on Availability	Website analytics are to remain closed and available only to the INSPIRE consortium and the EU Commission as it is useful only for internal reporting purposes. In case statistics are shared, data will be aggregated and anonymised before being made openly available, while personal data will be treated as expected by the GDPR. Data from newsletter subscriptions will remain closed as it contains personal information and is useful only for internal reporting purposes. Only aggregated information on website to be available through D6.4.
Accessible through	INSPIRE website
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	October 2027 (After approval of the respective deliverable)
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Utility to project partners to produce evidence-based results and ultimately achieve the objectives of the project.
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 1	Monitoring and assessment of the social media dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement activities
Task	T6.1 / Q-PLAN
Data	Social Media statistics
Availability	Closed & Open
Notes on Availability	Social media analytics to remain closed and available only to INSPIRE consortium and the EU Commission as it is useful only for internal reporting purposes. In case statistics are shared, data will be aggregated and anonymised before being made openly available, while personal data will be

	treated as expected by the GDPR. Only aggregated information on results to be available through D6.4.
Accessible through	INSPIRE website
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	October 2027 (After approval of the respective deliverable)
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Utility to project partners to produce evidence-based results and ultimately achieve the objectives of the project.
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 1	Monitoring and assessment of dissemination and communication activities and events
Task	T6.1 / Q-PLAN
Data	Data collected from dissemination and communication activities and events
Availability	Closed & Open
Notes on Availability	Data collected from dissemination and communication actions to remain closed and be available only to INSPIRE consortium and the EU Commission as it is useful only for internal reporting purposes. In case there is a need to share information for dissemination and communication purposes, any personal information will be anonymised before being made openly available. Only aggregated information on results to be available through D6.4.
Accessible through	INSPIRE website
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	October 2027 (After approval of the respective deliverable)
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Utility to project partners to produce evidence-based results and ultimately achieve the objectives of the project.
Other useful information	N/A

Activity 1	Project Synergies Identification and Engagement
Task	T6.2/ERDN
Data	Project Synergies Database
Availability	Open (anonymised summary available publicly)
Notes on Availability	The complete dataset (including specific project contact details) will remain closed to protect privacy, but an anonymised summary of identified synergies will be made openly available.
Accessible through	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> INSPIRE website Zenodo repository
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	April 2025
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	Useful for researchers, policymakers, and Horizon Europe beneficiaries interested in collaboration, best practices, and enhancing rural social inclusion through project synergies.
Other useful information	The summary dataset will list project objectives, thematic overlaps, and general opportunities for collaboration, providing insights for similar initiatives without compromising the privacy of individual project contacts.

3.5.7 WP7 Data collection/generation activities

Activity 1	Data generated through management and coordination actions
Task	T7.1, T7.2, T7.3, T7.4 / WR
Data	Names and e-mails of the INSPIRE consortium and financial information for companies, such as bank accounts.
Availability	Closed

Notes on Availability	To remain closed because such data will contain sensitive information. The data will be available only to the INSPIRE consortium. Some datasets will be available only to White Research.
Accessible through	Google Drive (cases of closed datasets being only available within the consortium).
Expected time for making data open (if applicable)	N/A
Data utility (to external stakeholders)	N/A
Other useful information	N/A

4. Allocation of resources

4.1 Estimated costs of making data fair

To assess the costs for making data FAIR in the context of INSPIRE, a series of **assumptions** was made, considering the respective **guidelines** provided by the Research Data Management Support, a multidisciplinary network of data experts within Utrecht University¹⁵, as well as of the UK Data Service and its data management costing tool¹⁶. In particular, the data management activities taken under consideration are presented below:

- **Data collection** costs cover activities necessary for acquiring external datasets (if required), gathering / generating new data, transcribing (if applicable), formatting and organising this data as well as acquiring informed consent from data subjects. This data processing activity reflects most of the costs required for making data FAIR as most of the project's data constitutes new data collected / generated over the course of the project.
- **Data documentation** costs address the effort required for describing data (e.g., marking data with variable and value labels, code descriptions, etc.) as well as creating well-defined metadata along with a meaningful description of the context and methodology of how data was collected/generated and processed (where necessary).
- **Data storage** costs include both the resources required for ensuring adequate storage space for the data as well as the effort necessary for conducting data back-ups.
- **Data access and security** costs involve costs related to ensuring access to the data as well as for protecting it from unauthorised access or use or from disclosure. Given that the storage of INSPIRE's data will not require the procurement of additional space (other than what is already available to project partners) as well as that no special measures or software are required to access and secure the data (other than what is inherently built into the repositories of INSPIRE's data), such costs are kept to a minimum.
- **Data preservation** costs, on the other hand, are estimated relatively higher than data storage, access and security costs, as additional effort will be required in several cases in order to convert the collected/generated data from their original form (e.g., physical interview transcripts) to an open and/or machine-readable format suitable for long-term preservation (e.g., to an .xlsx format.).
- **Data availability and re-use** costs is also foreseen to safeguard the appropriate digitisation and anonymisation of the data as well as cover any resources required for data sharing and cleaning. Along the same lines, appropriate effort is foreseen **for overall data management** as well, in order to cover the effort related with the operationalisation of data management in the framework of INSPIRE.

The costs for making the project's data FAIR, as described above, cover data-related activities and resources across the data lifecycle, spanning from collection and documentation through storage and preservation over to sharing and re-use. **All aforementioned costs were assessed and are foreseen to be covered within the project's allocated budget for each work package.** Long-term preservation costs, in the framework of INSPIRE, are assumed to be negligible since the open data of the project will be hosted in the INSPIRE project website.

¹⁵ Research Data Management Support. Guides: Costs of data management. Utrecht University. Retrieved from: <https://www.uu.nl/en/research/research-data-management/guides/costs-of-data-management>.

¹⁶ UK Data Service. Costing Data Management. Retrieved from: <https://www.ukdataservice.ac.uk/manage-data/plan/costing>.

4.2 Data management responsibilities

Effective, proper, and secure handling of the INSPIRE data collected/generated requires the establishment of specific data management roles within the data management methodology and procedures of the project. These responsibilities are outlined in this section of the DMP as follows.

Project Coordinator (PC): The PC, White Research SRL, is responsible for overall data management in the framework of INSPIRE, including the elaboration of the DMP and its updates (when necessary, along with support of all partners). At the same time, the PC is responsible for the elaboration of proper templates for the Informed Consent Form and Information Sheet (**updated version presented in Annex II**) to be appropriately adjusted and utilised by project partners during the relevant activities of the project. The Ethics Mentor of the project will provide guidance on proper adjustments of the Consent Form and Information Sheet that will be needed in each pilot context to avoid scientific misconduct and to respect limitations of research participants in a vulnerable situation to give consent autonomously and consciously.

Moreover, the PC is responsible for the project's Privacy Policy (**initial version presented in Annex I**) that will be uploaded on the project's website. The PC, in collaboration with the relevant project partners (e.g., Task Leaders), will examine if additional specific privacy policies are required for certain project's tasks and will coordinate the elaboration of such privacy policies. Finally, the PC coordinates with Work Package and Task Leaders to determine whether and how the data collected/generated by the project are shared and become available for re-use, contributes to its quality assurance, and uploads the project's openly available data to the INSPIRE project website.

Work Package Leaders (WPL): The WPL are responsible for coordinating the implementation of the data processing activities performed under the WPs they are leading. They align with the PC and the respective Work Task Leader on whether and how the data gathered/produced under the tasks that fall within the WP they are leading will be shared and/or re-used. This includes the definition of access procedures, as well as potential embargo periods along with any necessary software and/or other tools which may be required for data sharing and re-use. Finally, the WPL are the main responsible for assuring the quality of the data stemming from the activities of the WP they are leading, including assessing their quality and indicating any need for improvement to the respective Task Leaders.

Task Leaders (TL): TLs are responsible for the data collected / generated in the frame of the tasks that fall under their leadership as well as for safeguarding their appropriate and timely processing. Moreover, they are responsible for properly adjusting the Informed Consent Form (*Annex II*) and Data Subject Request Form templates (*Annex III*), to the needs and specificities of the activities carried out in the task they are leading. TLs are responsible to identify the need for a specific privacy policy regarding the task they are leading and collaborate with the PC for drafting and publicise it. Finally, they undertake any necessary actions to prepare the data collected / generated through the tasks they are leading for sharing either within the consortium or openly (including the use of proper naming conventions, application of suitable anonymisation techniques, creation of appropriate metadata and documentation, etc.).

Partners: All project partners (especially the 6 pilot partners: PEDAL, ERDN, LADAPT, MEDINA, WHEEL, ROM) are tasked to collect, digitise, anonymise, store, destroy and / or otherwise process data for the specific purpose of the activity in which it has been collected / generated within the

framework of the project. They are responsible for appropriately collecting the necessary consent for processing data as well as for ensuring that the Informed Consent Form (*Annex II*) and the Data Subject Request Form (*Annex III*) used to this end are properly adjusted to the needs of the activity they are participating (including references to project's Privacy Policy and any other applicable specific privacy policies) and, in any particularities, applicable to their organisation while ensuring adherence to provisions of National Data Protection Legislation in their respective country. Moreover, they are responsible for managing the consents they have collected with a view to demonstrating their compliance with the relevant applicable EU and national regulation. Finally, they perform quality checks to assess and maintain the quality of the dataset(s) held within their records.

Data party: As defined under Art.11 of the Consortium Agreement, a Data Party is the Party that is responsible to fulfil the Data Subjects' Rights. The Party leading each data processing activity is specified in this Data Management Plan, in the table below. In general, the Data Party shall be: (i) in processing activities carried out solely by one Party, this Party will be the "Data Party", (ii) in processing activities that more Parties are involved, the Data Party shall be the one that collects the personal data from the data subjects and has the first contact with them, except otherwise agreed by the Parties. The Data Party(ies) bears the responsibility to: (i) support the data subjects and act as a contact point for them in exercising their rights under applicable data protection regulation(s) (such as Articles 15 to 22 GDPR); (ii) provide the data subjects with the information required by applicable data protection regulation(s) (such as Articles 13 and 14 of the GDPR). The role and responsibilities of the Data Party is further detailed under Art. 11 of the CA.

Data repositories: Data repositories are tasked with the storage and long-term preservation of the project's data. In this respect, INSPIRE website maintains and preserves the openly available data of INSPIRE enabling its sharing and re-use.

For each activity that involves processing of personal data, one of the Parties is designated as Data Party and specified as such in the following "Record of Processing Activities" table. The following table illustrates the **allocation of data management responsibilities** amongst the members of the INSPIRE consortium per data collected/generated under each WP. In general, the Data Party shall be the Party that collects the personal data from the data subjects and has the first and main contact with them. In personal data processing activities where more than one Party is involved, apart from the Data Party, all involved Parties together with the type of involvement are defined and specified in the "Record of Processing Activities" table.

The present table has been completed based on the information available at the beginning of the project. During the project implementation, new or different allocations of responsibilities among partners may be identified and revised accordingly. When there are changes in the project activities that involve data processing, the Record of Processing Activities in the Data Management Plan will be updated accordingly and be subject to an approval procedure, as detailed by Art.11 in the Consortium Agreement.

Table 4. Record of Processing Activities

#	Name of activity	Data	Tasks	Data source	Data Category(ies)	Data partners
1	Systematic review on social exclusion in rural areas	Data collected through systematic review	T1.1	Publicly available sources	Demographics; other	Task leader (SEERC)
2	Forecast of trends and drivers of social exclusion in rural areas	Data collected through Delphi Exercise	T1.2	Data subject	Experts' opinions; other	Task leader (Q-PLAN)
3	Identification of expert participants for the Delphi exercise	Data collected through desk research	T1.2	Publicly available sources & consortium partners	Contact details; professional information; demographics	Task leader (Q-PLAN) + Partners involved in data collection processes each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.
4	National survey on social exclusion	Data collected through quantitative survey	T1.3	Data subject	Contact details; professional information; demographics; philosophical beliefs; other	Task leader (RUG) + Pilot partners involved in data collection processes (ERDN, PEDAL, WHEEL, MEDINA, ROM, LADAPT) each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.
5	National interviews with QH stakeholders	Data collected through qualitative interview guide	T1.3	Data subject	Contact details; professional information; demographics; philosophical beliefs; images; other	Task leader (RUG) + Pilot partners involved in data collection processes (ERDN, PEDAL, WHEEL, MEDINA, ROM, LADAPT) each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.
6	CATI surveys for micro-level data	Data collected through CATI survey	T1.4	Data subject	Contact details; professional information; demographics; philosophical beliefs; other	Task leader (UB) + Pilot partners involved in data collection processes (ERDN, PEDAL, WHEEL, MEDINA, ROM, LADAPT) each

						being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines. Task leader (UB) + Pilot partners involved in data collection
7	Observational fieldwork	Data collected through observational fieldwork and traditional ethnographic research	T1.4	Data subject	Contact details; professional information; demographics; philosophical beliefs; images; other	processes (ERDN, PEDAL, WHEEL, MEDINA, ROM, LADAPT) each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines. Task leader (UB) + Pilot partners involved in data collection
8	Paper-based surveys for micro-level data	Data collected through quantitative paper-based survey	T1.4	Data subject	Contact details; professional information; demographics; philosophical beliefs; other	Task leader (UB) + Pilot partners involved in data collection processes (ERDN, PEDAL, WHEEL, MEDINA, ROM, LADAPT) each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.
9	Typology on social wellbeing, resilience and exclusion of European rural areas	Data collected combining results from T1.2, T1.3, and T1.4	T1.5	Data subject	Delphi results	Task leader (UB) + Pilot partners involved in data collection processes (ERDN, PEDAL, WHEEL, MEDINA, ROM, LADAPT)
				Data subject	National survey results	
				Data subject	Semi-structured interviews results	
				Data subject	Observational fieldwork results	
				Data subject	CATI surveys results	
10	Desk research	Data collected through desk research	T2.1	Data subject	Paper-based surveys results	Task leader (ESN) + Partners involved in data collection
				Publicly available sources	Demographics; other	

11	Semi-structured Interviews	Data collected through qualitative interview guide	T2.1	Data subject	Contact details; professional information; demographics; philosophical beliefs; images; other	processes each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines. Task leader (ESN) + Pilot partners involved in data collection processes (ERDN, PEDAL, WHEEL, MEDINA, ROM, LADAPT) each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.
12	Focus groups	Data collected through qualitative interview guide for focus groups	T2.1	Data subject	Contact details; professional information; demographics; philosophical beliefs; images; other	Task leader (ESN) + Pilot partners involved in data collection processes (ERDN, PEDAL, WHEEL, MEDINA, ROM, LADAPT) each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.
13	Conceptual definitions and legal frameworks of social economy in the EU	Data collected through desk research	T2.2	Publicly available sources	Demographics; other	Task leader (SEE) + Partners involved in data collection processes each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.
14	Impact frameworks at global, EU and national level to evaluate social economy services	Data collected through desk research	T2.2	Publicly available sources	Demographics; other	Task leader (SEE) + Partners involved in data collection processes each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.
15	Digital ethnography	Data collected by combining digital ethnography	T2.3	Data subject	Digital ethnography; demographics; other	Task leader (RUG) + Partners involved in data collection

		with desk research, semi-structured interviews, and observational fieldwork		Publicly available sources	Desk research results	processes each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.
				Data subject	Semi-structured interviews results	
					Observational fieldwork results	
16	Microsimulation – agent-based modelling	Data collected by combining digital ethnography with results from the various social exclusion surveys	T2.3	Data subject	Digital ethnography results	Task leader (RUG) + Partners involved in data collection processes each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.
				Data subject	Results of surveys from WP1	
17	Pilot area environmental and needs assessment	Data collected through desk research	T3.1	Publicly available sources	Demographics; other	Task leader (CZU) + Pilot partners involved in data collection processes (ERDN, PEDAL, WHEEL, MEDINA, ROM, LADAPT) each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.
18	Targeted community engagement and vulnerability assessment	Data collected through desk research	T3.1	Publicly available sources	Demographics; other	Task leader (CZU) + Pilot partners involved in data collection processes (ERDN, PEDAL, WHEEL, MEDINA, ROM, LADAPT) each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.
19	Local awareness raising campaigns in 7 pilot areas	Data collected through engagement techniques	T3.2	Data subject	Contact details; professional information; demographics; philosophical beliefs; images; other	Task leader (WR) + Pilot partners involved in data collection processes (ERDN, PEDAL, WHEEL, MEDINA, ROM, LADAPT) each being responsible

						for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.
20	Local co-creation workshops on Smart Village Labs in 7 pilot areas	Data collected through co-creation activities	T3.2	Data subject	Contact details; professional information; demographics; philosophical beliefs; images; other	Task leader (WR) + Pilot partners involved in data collection processes (ERDN, PEDAL, WHEEL, MEDINA, ROM, LADAPT) each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.
21	User-innovation workshops	Data collected through the two user-innovation workshops per pilot area	T3.3	Data subject	Contact details; professional information; demographics; philosophical beliefs; images; other	Task leader (MEDINA) + Pilot partners involved in data collection processes (ERDN, PEDAL, WHEEL, ROM, LADAPT) each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.
22	Sustaining the Smart Village labs	Data collected through co-creation workshops	T3.4	Data subject	Personal opinions; other	Task leader (Q-PLAN) + Pilot partners involved in data collection processes (ERDN, PEDAL, MEDINA, WHEEL, ROM, LADAPT) each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.
23	Identification of key stakeholder participants for the local sustainability workshops	Data collected through desk research	T3.4	Publicly available sources & consortium partners	Contact details; professional information; demographics; other	Task leader (Q-PLAN) + Partners involved in data collection processes each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.
24	Development of service programmes	Data collected by combining the	T4.1	Data subject	WP1 research results	Task leader (KOC) + Partners involved in data

findings of WP1,
WP2,
and T3.2

Data subject
WP2 research
results

Data subject
T3.2
engagement
results

collection
processes each
being responsible
for the data they
collect, as per the
task leader's
guidelines.

25	Needs assessment of lab participants	Data collected through questionnaires	T4.2	Data subject	Contact details; professional information; demographics; philosophical beliefs; other	Task leader (PEDAL) + Pilot partners involved in data collection processes (ERDN, MEDINA, WHEEL, ROM, LADAPT) each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.
26	Field visits and case studies	Data collected through observational fieldwork	T4.2	Data subject	Contact details; professional information; demographics; philosophical beliefs; other	Task leader (PEDAL) + Pilot partners involved in data collection processes (ERDN, MEDINA, WHEEL, ROM, LADAPT) each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.
27	Co-design sessions	Data collected through a combination of note-taking, photographic documentation, surveys and questionnaires, post-session Interviews	T4.2	Data subject	Contact details; professional information; demographics; philosophical beliefs; images; other	Task leader (PEDAL) + Pilot partners involved in data collection processes (ERDN, MEDINA, WHEEL, ROM, LADAPT) each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.
28	Events	Data collected through a combination of note-taking, photographic documentation, surveys and questionnaires, post-session Interviews	T4.2	Data subject	Contact details; professional information; demographics; philosophical beliefs; images; other	Task leader (PEDAL) + Pilot partners involved in data collection processes (ERDN, MEDINA, WHEEL, ROM, LADAPT) each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.

29	Pilot and scale up demonstration report	Data collected through informal interviews and observation of pilot stakeholders	T4.3	Data subject	Contact details; professional information; demographics; philosophical beliefs; images; other	Task leader (WHEEL) + Pilot partners involved in data collection processes (ERDN, MEDINA, PEDAL, ROM, LADAPT) each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.
30	Quantitative data collection for evaluation of Smart Village Labs' impact	Data collected through quantitative survey	T4.4	Data subject	Contact details; professional information; demographics; philosophical beliefs; other	Task leader (WR) + Pilot partners involved in data collection processes (ERDN, MEDINA, PEDAL, WHEEL, ROM, LADAPT) each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.
31	Qualitative data collection for evaluation of Smart Village Labs' impact	Data collected through qualitative interviews	T4.4	Data subject	Contact details; professional information; demographics; philosophical beliefs; other	Task leader (WR) + Pilot partners involved in data collection processes (ERDN, MEDINA, PEDAL, WHEEL, ROM, LADAPT) each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.
32	Network of Interest stakeholder engagement	Data collected through a combination of stakeholder interviews, surveys, and desk research	T5.1	Data subject	Contact details; professional information; demographics; philosophical beliefs; other	Task leader (ERDN) + Partners involved in data collection processes each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.
33	Network interaction records	Data collected through a combination of stakeholder interviews, surveys, and desk research	T5.1	Data subject	Contact details; professional information; demographics; philosophical beliefs; images; other	Task leader (ERDN) + Partners involved in data collection processes each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.

				Publicly available sources	Results of typology	
34	Creation of the Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard	Data collected by combining the findings of T1.5, T2.4, and T5.1	T5.2	Publicly available sources Data subject	Results of Atlas Contact details; professional information; demographics; philosophical beliefs; other	Task leader (SEERC) + Partners involved in data collection processes each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.
35	Replication of INSPIRE activities in follower cases	Data collected by combining the findings from all previous WPs	T5.3	Data subject & Publicly available sources	Results from all previous WPs of INSPIRE	Task leader (WR) + Partners involved in all previous data collection processes each being responsible for the data they collect, as per the task leader's guidelines.
36	Monitoring and assessment of the website's dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement activities	Data generated through dissemination and communication activities by the Dissemination Manager	T6.1	Data subject & INSPIRE website	Google Analytics, Mailchimp Analytics	Task leader (Q-PLAN)
37	Monitoring and assessment of the social media dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement activities	Data generated through dissemination and communication activities by the Dissemination Manager	T6.1	Data subject & INSPIRE social media accounts	Social Media Analytics	Task leader (Q-PLAN)
38	Monitoring and assessment of dissemination and communication activities and events	Data generated through dissemination and communication activities by the INSPIRE consortium	T6.1	INSPIRE partners & Web sources	Videos; word documents; images; notes; other monitoring metrics	Task leader (Q-PLAN) + Partners participating or deploying D&C activities and events and thus involved in data collection

						processes (all partners) each being responsible for the data they collect and their anonymisation
39	Project Synergies Identification and Engagement	Data generated through synergising activities by the INSPIRE consortium	T6.2	INSPIRE partners & Data subject	Videos; word documents; images; minutes; other monitoring metrics	Task leader (ERDN) + Partners involved in data collection processes (all partners) each being responsible for the data they collect and their anonymisation
20	Data generated through management and coordination actions	Data generated through management and coordination	T7.1-T7.4	Data subject	Contact details; professional information; images; minutes	Task leader (WR) + Partners involved in data collection processes (All partners) each being responsible for the data they collect

4.2.1 Data sharing

As stated by Article 11.3 of the INSPIRE CA, in general, the following rules apply to data processing and sharing:

- Only a shared database of contact details of stakeholders relevant to the project activities and future similar projects will be shared at the consortium level and will be made available on the online shared repository. New contact details can be added to the list only if the relevant consent form is collected and uploaded to the folder.
- No other type of personal data (including philosophical and political opinions) will be made available for 12 months after the project’s end on the online project repository. All data that is uploaded on the project folder must be anonymised in accordance with the principles laid out in the data protection regulation (Recital 26 GDPR).
- If more than one Party shares access to the same dataset, the Parties involved in the data processing activity may choose an appropriate mean for sharing the data outside the project folder, ensuring the process follows adequate security measures in compliance with the GDPR provisions.

5. Data security

Detailed information on how the INSPIRE project securely handles data is provided in a dedicated document entitled “**INSPIRE Privacy Policy**”. This is a living document which will be updated and enhanced when needed over the project’s lifecycle.

INSPIRE will **securely handle any collected/generated data** throughout its entire lifecycle as it is essential to safeguard this data against accidental loss and/or unauthorised access and manipulation. To achieve this the project will apply appropriate technical and organisational measures based on a risk assessment of the relevant data that takes into account the impact and the likelihood of a potential data breach. With that in mind, the project’s data security strategy aims at minimising the probability that a data breach will occur during the course and after the completion of INSPIRE, either from human error or hardware failure, as well as inhibit any unauthorised access.

Particularly, in case of personal data collection/generation it is crucial that this **data can only be accessed by those authorised to do so**. With that in mind, the project’s back-up and data recovery strategy aims at ensuring that no data loss will occur during the course and after the completion of INSPIRE, either from human error or hardware failure, as well as inhibit any unauthorised access.

All project partners are responsible for processing¹⁷ data using appropriate means, such as private servers or cloud service providers that adhere to the relevant legal data protection requirements (e.g., GDPR) and will ensure that this **data is protected**, and any **necessary data security controls have been implemented**, to minimise the risk of information leak and destruction. This case refers to the data that will be closed and therefore will not be shared and / or re-used within the framework of the project. In this case, to minimise the consequences of potential data losses, the data will be **backed up at regular time intervals based on change frequency and criticality**. The **backed-up files will be stored in appropriate storage media including external hard drives, flash drives, NAS devices and reputable cloud services**, so as to safeguard their preservation, while also enabling their recovery at any time. Moreover, **integrity checks**¹⁸ will be carried out regularly ensuring that the stored data has not been changed or corrupted.

Access to closed data will only be permitted to authorised project partners. In case there is a **personal data breach**, the responsible **project partner will notify, without undue delay** and, where feasible, **not later than 72 hours after having become aware of it, its competent national supervisory authority** (e.g., data protection authority) **as well as the data subject(s) that may be affected by the breach**. Moreover, the responsible partner will document any personal data breaches, including information such as the facts relevant to the breach, its effects and the remedial action(s) taken.

Identification and authentication access controls play an important role in the context of the project, as they help partners to protect the data collected/generated during INSPIRE and especially personal data. To this end, each project partner is responsible for and committed to ensuring the application of

¹⁷ Processing, according to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament (General Data Protection Regulation), means any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction.

¹⁸ An integrity check is the process of comparing the current state of stored data and/or programs to a previously recorded state in order to detect any changes.

appropriate access controls to the data they are processing within their private servers of their organisation.

The Project's website will be developed by a professional web designer by M6 in WordPress and managed by Q-PLAN (Dissemination Manager) only. Therefore, more information on the website and newsletter data security will be included in the second version of the DMP.

As detailed earlier in the document, the website and newsletter will follow rules set in the INSPIRE Privacy Policy which will be updated-enhanced when needed over the project's lifecycle.

6. Ethical aspects and other procedures

This Chapter concerns with the ethical aspect of the INSPIRE DMP and the ethical compliance of the underlying data foreseen to be collected/generated under the project's activities. The project will process data that are not included in any special category of personal data¹⁹ (i.e., non-sensitive data) according to relevant data protection legislation (e.g., GDPR). As mentioned above it is complemented by Work Package seven (WP7) deliverables, which cover ethical considerations in more detail.

In accordance with the **Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 (GDPR)**, all personal data processed for project's activities shall be:

- processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject;
- collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes relative to project's objectives and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes;
- adequate, relevant, and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed;
- accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date;
- kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed;
- processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data (see section 4).

For all personal data processing activities within the framework of the project at least one lawful basis as of Art. 6 GDPR applies. Where informed consent is chosen as the lawful basis for processing, all relevant provisions of the data protection legislation (e.g., Art.7 GDPR) are observed.

No transfer of personal data outside the EU is foreseen as part of project's implementation. In case of data storage providers situated both inside and outside the EEA, partners are committed to ensure their compliance with the relevant GDPR requirements before starting using their services.

The templates for the Information Sheet and the Informed Consent Form, used in the implementation of the project's activities, are compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation and annexed to this DMP (see *Annex II*).

Note:

It is important to highlight that each project partner is responsible for ensuring that the templates for **the Information Sheet** as well as **the Informed Consent Form** are appropriately adjusted according to (i) the needs of the activity for which they are being used by them as well as to (ii) the relevant regulations applicable to their respective countries and/or organisation. Moreover, **all partners have the duty to keep records to demonstrate that an individual has consented to processing of their personal data** and use consent management mechanisms that make it easy for individuals to withdraw their consent.

¹⁹ Special categories of personal data according to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament (General Data Protection Regulation) include personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation.

7. Conclusions

This first version of the INSPIRE DMP aims at safeguarding the sound management of the data collected/generated during the project's activities across their entire lifecycle, while also making them compatible with the FAIR scheme. It describes all the underlying processes of the INSPIRE data management, collection, and generation, in accordance with the GDPR guidelines, and sheds light on (i) the data being collected/generated under the project activities, (ii) the specific objectives under which each dataset is collected/generated, (iii) the allocation of resources and data management responsibilities and (iv) the data security and ethical aspects of the data.

In the framework of INSPIRE, the DMP is a living document and is updated throughout the course of the project, considering its latest developments and available results. It is expected to be further developed and updated throughout the duration of INSPIRE. If necessary, additional ad hoc updates may be realised in order to include new data, better detail and/or reflect modifications in the methodologies applied or other aspects relevant to data management (such as costs for making data FAIR, size of data, etc.), changes in consortium policies and plans or other potential external factors.

Annexes

Annex 1: INSPIRE Privacy Policy

How we collect your personal data

We collect personal data both **directly** and **indirectly**:

Directly: We obtain personal data directly from individuals in a variety of ways, including but not limited to the following cases:

- an individual registers to attend in meetings and events we host and during attendance at such events;
- an individual participates in an interview or survey organised by us;
- an individual subscribes to our project newsletter;
- we establish cooperative relationships with an individual;
- we provide professional services pursuant to our contract with the European Commission.

Indirectly: We obtain personal data indirectly about individuals from a variety of sources, including:

- our research partners;
- our networks and contacts;
- public and open data sources such as public registers, news articles and internet searches;
- social and professional networking sites (e.g., LinkedIn).

What types of data we collect

We only collect the data that are necessary for the smooth implementation of our project. These data fall into the following categories:

- **contact details** (name/surname, e-mail address, phone number);
- **professional information** (job title, organisation, field of expertise);
- **demographics** (e.g. age, gender, nationality, income level);
- information about what a person **knows or believes**;
- **videos and photos** (from people that attend our events).

Technical means of data collection

Your personal data may be collected on publicly available websites, through partners' databases, via surveying software (e.g., Google Forms, EU Survey, SurveyMonkey) and via direct enquiry to you during project activities (e.g., participation in focus groups, face-to-face interviews, observational fieldwork). Should we collect your personal data in any other way than through direct inquiry with you, we will make sure to inform you about this and about the source of the data.

Bases of lawful processing

We process personal data on the following legal bases:

- **Legal obligations** - for processing activities required for compliance both with applicable national and European legislation as well as with the specific legal and regulatory framework of the Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation of the European Union.
- **Consent** – for processing activities such as organisation of surveys, focus groups, and interviews, completion of questionnaires, and dissemination of project's results.
- **Contractual obligations** - for processing activities such as reporting to the European Commission and complying with project's publicity obligations.

What we do with your personal data

We process your personal data with the purpose of:

- Conducting research (e.g., interviews, focus groups, surveys);
- Disseminating our project's results to different types of stakeholders;
- Sending invitations and providing access to guests attending our events and webinars;
- Administering, maintaining, and ensuring the security of our information systems, applications, and websites;
- Processing online requests or queries, including responding to communications from individuals;
- Complying with contractual, legal, and regulatory obligations.

How we secure your personal data when process it

We apply a personal data risk assessment process to identify, analyse, and evaluate the security risks that may threaten your personal data. Based on the results of this risk assessment, we define and apply a set of both technical and organisational measures to mitigate the above security risks, including but not limited to:

- Data Protection Policies to guide our personnel when processing your data;
- Written contracts with organisations that process personal data on our behalf;
- Non-Disclosure Agreements with our personnel;
- Back up process, anti-malware protection, access control mechanisms, etc.

Do we share personal data with third parties?

We may occasionally share personal data with trusted third parties to help us deliver efficient and quality services. When we do so, we ensure that recipients are contractually bound to safeguard the data we entrust to them before we share the data. We may engage with several or all the following categories of recipients:

- Parties that support us as we provide our services (e.g., cloud-based software services such as Google Drive, Dropbox, Microsoft SharePoint);
- Our professional advisers, including lawyers, auditors, and insurers;

- Dissemination services providers (e.g., Mailchimp);
- Law enforcement or other government and regulatory agencies or other third parties as required by, and in accordance with applicable law or regulation;
- The European Commission, according to our relevant contractual obligations (e.g., Grant Agreement, Consortium Agreement).

Do we transfer your personal data outside the European Economic Area?

We do not own file servers located outside the European Economic Area (EEA). However, some partners may use cloud and / or marketing services from reputable providers such as Google Drive, SharePoint, Dropbox, Mailchimp, etc., situated both inside and outside the EEA. We always check that such providers comply with the relevant GDPR requirements before starting using their services.

INSPIRE website Privacy Policy

INSPIRE project website: <https://inspire.eu/> (the correct website link will be made available on M6)

In INSPIRE, accessible from <https://inspire.eu/> (the correct website link will be made available on M6), one of our main priorities is the privacy of our visitors. This Privacy Policy document contains types of information that is collected and recorded by INSPIRE and how we use it.

If you have additional questions or require more information about our Privacy Policy, do not hesitate to contact us.

This Privacy Policy applies only to our online activities and is valid for visitors to our website with regards to the information that they shared and/or collected in INSPIRE. This policy is not applicable to any information collected offline or via channels other than this website.

Consent

By using our website, you hereby consent to our Privacy Policy and agree to its terms.

Information we collect

The personal information that you are asked to provide, and the reasons why you are asked to provide it, will be made clear to you at the point we ask you to provide your personal information.

If you contact us directly, we may receive additional information about you such as your name, email address, phone number, the contents of the message and/or attachments you may send us, and any other information you may choose to provide.

When you register for an Account, we may ask for your contact information, including items such as name, company name, address, email address, and telephone number.

How we use your information

We use the information we collect in various ways, including to:

- Provide, operate, and maintain our website
- Improve, personalise, and expand our website
- Understand and analyse how you use our website
- Develop new products, services, features, and functionality

- Communicate with you, either directly or through one of our partners, including for customer service, to provide you with updates and other information relating to the website, and for marketing and promotional purposes
- Send you emails
- Find and prevent fraud

Log Files

INSPIRE follows a standard procedure of using log files. These files log visitors when they visit websites. All hosting companies do this as a part of hosting services' analytics. The information collected by log files include internet protocol (IP) addresses, browser type, Internet Service Provider (ISP), date and time stamp, referring/exit pages, and possibly the number of clicks. These are not linked to any information that is personally identifiable. The purpose of the information is for analysing trends, administering the site, tracking users' movement on the website, and gathering demographic information.

Cookies and Web Beacons

Like any other website, INSPIRE uses "cookies". These cookies are used to store information including visitors' preferences, and the pages on the website that the visitor accessed or visited. The information is used to optimise the users' experience by customising our web page content based on visitors' browser type and/or other information.

GDPR Data Protection Rights

We would like to make sure you are fully aware of all of your data protection rights. Every user is entitled to the following:

- The right to access – You have the right to request copies of your personal data. We may charge you a small fee for this service.
- The right to rectification – You have the right to request that we correct any information you believe is inaccurate. You also have the right to request that we complete the information you believe is incomplete.
- The right to erasure – You have the right to request that we erase your personal data, under certain conditions.
- The right to restrict processing – You have the right to request that we restrict the processing of your personal data, under certain conditions.
- The right to object to processing – You have the right to object to our processing of your personal data, under certain conditions.
- The right to data portability – You have the right to request that we transfer the data that we have collected to another organisation, or directly to you, under certain conditions.

If you make a request, we have one month to respond to you. If you would like to exercise any of these rights, please contact us.

Children's Information

Another part of our priority is adding protection for children while using the internet. We encourage parents and guardians to observe, participate in, and/or monitor and guide their online activity.

INSPIRE does not knowingly collect any Personal Identifiable Information from children under the age of 13. If you think that your child provided this kind of information on our website, we strongly encourage you to contact us immediately and we will do our best efforts to promptly remove such information from our records.

Changes to This Privacy Policy

We may update our Privacy Policy from time to time. Thus, we advise you to review the INSPIRE website page periodically for any changes. We will notify you of any changes by posting the new

Privacy Policy on this page. These changes are effective immediately, after they are posted on this page.

Contact Us

If you have any questions or suggestions about our Privacy Policy, do not hesitate to contact us at info@inspire.eu (the correct mail address will be made available on M6).

INSPIRE website Cookies Policy

This is the Cookie Policy for INSPIRE, accessible from [\[cookies policy on website URL to be available by M6\]](#).

What Are Cookies

As is common practice with almost all professional websites, this site uses cookies, which are tiny files that are downloaded to your computer, to improve your experience. This page describes what information they gather, how we use it and why we sometimes need to store these cookies. We will also share how you can prevent these cookies from being stored, however this may downgrade or 'break' certain elements of the site's functionality.

How We Use Cookies

We use cookies for a variety of reasons detailed below. Unfortunately, in most cases there are no industry standard options for disabling cookies without completely disabling the functionality and features they add to this site. It is recommended that you leave on all cookies if you are not sure whether you need them or not in case they are used to provide a service that you use.

Disabling Cookies

You can prevent the setting of cookies by adjusting the settings on your browser (see your browser Help for how to do this). Be aware that disabling cookies will affect the functionality of this and many other websites that you visit. Disabling cookies will usually result in also disabling certain functionality and features of this site. Therefore, it is recommended that you do not disable cookies.

The Cookies We Set

- ❖ **Email newsletters related cookies:** This site offers newsletter or email subscription services and cookies may be used to remember if you are already registered and whether to show certain notifications which might only be valid to subscribed/unsubscribed users.
- ❖ **Forms related cookies:** When you submit data by using a form such as the forms that are found on contact pages or comment forms, then cookies may be set to remember your user details for future correspondence.

Third Party Cookies

- In some special cases we also use cookies provided by trusted third parties. The following section details which third party cookies you might encounter through this site.
- This site uses Google Analytics which is one of the most widespread and trusted analytics solutions on the web for helping us to understand how you use the site and ways that we can improve your experience. These cookies may track things such as how long you spend on the site and the pages that you visit so we can continue to produce engaging content.
- For more information on Google Analytics cookies, see the official Google Analytics page.
- Third party analytics are used to track and measure usage of this site so that we can continue to produce engaging content. These cookies may track things such as how long you spend on the site or pages you visit which helps us to understand how we can improve the site for you.

- From time to time, we test new features and make subtle changes to the way that the site is delivered. When we are still testing new features, these cookies may be used to ensure that you receive a consistent experience whilst on the site, also ensuring that we understand which optimisations our users appreciate the most.
- We also use social media buttons and/or plugins on this site that allow you to connect with your social network in various ways. For these to work, we will set cookies through our site which may be used to enhance your profile on their site or contribute to the data they hold for various purposes outlined in their respective privacy policies.

More Information

Hopefully that has clarified things for you and as was previously mentioned if there is something that you are not sure whether you need or not it is usually safer to leave cookies enabled in case it does interact with one of the features you use on our site.

For more general information on cookies, please read the [Cookies Policy article](#).

However, if you are still looking for more information, you can contact us through one of our preferred contact methods:

Email: info@inspire.eu (the correct mail address will be made available on M6).

Your rights

You have the following rights regarding our processing of your personal data:

- **Right to withdraw consent** – You can withdraw consent that you have previously given to one or more specified purposes to process your personal data. This will not affect the lawfulness of any processing carried out before you withdraw your consent.
- **Right of access** – You can ask us to verify whether we are processing personal data about you and, if so, to have access to a copy of such data.
- **Right to rectification and erasure** – You can ask us to correct our records if you believe they contain incorrect or incomplete information about you or ask us to erase your personal data after you withdraw your consent to processing or when we no longer need it for the purpose it was originally collected.
- **Right to restriction of processing** – You can ask us to temporarily restrict our processing of your personal data if you contest the accuracy of your personal data, prefer to restrict its use rather than having us erase it, or need us to preserve it for you to establish, exercise or defend a legal claim. A temporary restriction may apply while verifying whether we have overriding legitimate grounds to process it. You can ask us to inform you before we lift that temporary processing restriction.
- **Right to data portability** – In some circumstances, where you have provided personal data to us, you can ask us to transmit that personal data (in a structured, commonly used, and machine-readable format) directly to another entity.
- **Right to object** – You can object to our use of your personal data for direct marketing purposes, including profiling or where processing has taken the form of automated decision-making. However, we may need to keep some minimal information (e.g., e-mail address) to comply with your request to cease marketing to you.
- **Right to make a complaint to your local Data Protection Authority (DPA)** regarding any concerns you may have about our data handling practices.
(see https://ec.europa.eu/justice/article-29/structure/data-protection-authorities/index_en.htm)

To ask us to do anything of the above, you can contact us by email: info@inspire.eu (the correct mail address will be made available on M6).

We will promptly examine your request against the relevant requirements of the laws and regulations governing privacy and personal data protection and we will answer the latest within 30 days after receiving your request. We will ask from you some kind of identification (e.g., photocopy of your identity card or passport) to avoid non-authorized reveal of your personal data. If, for reasons of complexity of the request or a multitude of requests, we are unable to respond promptly, we will notify you within 30 days of any delay, which in no case may exceed two months from the expiration of the 30-day deadline.

How long do we retain personal data?

We retain personal data to provide our services, stay in contact with you and to comply with applicable laws, regulations, and contractual obligations to which we are subject. Please note that we have an obligation to retain data concerning projects funded by the Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation of the European Union for up to five years after the end of the project (unless further retention is requested by auditors). After the expiry of the retention period, and unless further legitimate grounds for retention arise, we will dispose of personal data in a secure manner.

Disclaimer of liability for third party websites

Although our site may contain links to third-party sites, including the sites of the consortium partners, we are not responsible for the privacy practices or content of these sites, and we expressly disclaim any liability for any loss or damage that may be caused by the use of these links. We do not monitor the privacy practices or the content of these sites. If you have any questions about the privacy practices of another site, you should contact the site's responsible personnel. We suggest you read the privacy policy of each website you interact with, before allowing the collection and use of your personal data.

We may also provide social media features that allow you to share information on your social networks and interact with our project on various social media sites. The use of these social media features may result in the collection or sharing of information about you. We recommend that you check the privacy policies and regulations of the social networking sites you interact with, so that you can be sure that you understand what information may be collected, used, and disclosed by these sites.

Annex 2: INSPIRE Information Sheet and Consent Form

Information sheet

We would like to invite you to take part in an activity being carried out by INSPIRE, a 3-year project funded by the European Union within the framework of the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme. Before you decide to take part in our project's activity, please take some time to carefully read this information sheet and ask questions about anything you do not understand.

The project is funded under European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement no. 101136592. The project's call is HORIZON-CL6-2023-COMMUNITIES-01: Resilient, inclusive, healthy and green rural, coastal and urban communities.

About INSPIRE project

INSPIRE seeks to promote social inclusion and wellbeing in European rural areas through a blend of research, pilot innovation, and policy interventions. The project uses advanced methodologies and pilot deployment activities, including a multi-disciplinary conceptual framework of social inclusion that combines Computational Social Sciences with traditional data collection methods (e.g., ethnographic fieldwork) to cover hard-to-reach populations. The project also creates an advanced territorial typology of rural areas in Europe, and fosters social inclusion and empowerment by analysing successful service programmes, initiatives and policies and developing the Services and Social Economy Atlas on Rural Empowerment.

Based on the "Smart Village" concept, INSPIRE delivers Smart Village labs in 7 pilot areas, which represent diverse settings (rural, coastal, peri-urban, mountainous, etc.) and target groups. These labs connect multiple actors, provide capacity-building in various skills, support user innovation, and enhance industry-academia-state collaboration. The project tests real social economy solutions to enhance access to social services in the pilot areas, and to boost their local business ecosystems. Finally, the project develops the Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard to support informed policymaking and ensure social inclusion.

In this context, the core objectives of the INSPIRE project are:

- Examine the latest trends and challenges regarding social inclusion in rural areas.
- Map and analyse (social) service programmes, policies and initiatives, and social entrepreneurial models to understand advantages, potential and limitations in rural areas.
- Enhance existing governance frameworks for social inclusion and social economy in rural areas by establishing Smart Village Labs for multi-actor engagement in 7 pilot areas in Europe.
- Pilot and evaluate local social economy solutions in the 7 pilot areas to enhance social inclusion through better access to quality services.
- Equip policy makers with tools and policy recommendations to support social inclusion and access of groups in vulnerable situations to social services.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been invited to take part in the activity of the INSPIRE project because you are 18 years or older and you have been identified as a key stakeholder of the project. A stakeholder is either an

individual, group or organisation that is either impacted by the outcomes of the project and or has an interest in the success of the project.

Is my participation in the project's activity voluntary?

Your participation is entirely voluntary. If you decide to participate in the project's activity, we will ask you to **sign an INSPIRE Informed Consent Form** (provided in the next section) to collect and process your data. The project will last for 36 months but your involvement would only be for as long as you wish.

What are the benefits of my participation?

There may not be direct benefits for your participation in the activity (e.g., financial compensation). However, by participating in the project's activity, you are supporting the INSPIRE project members to better understand the factors that contribute to social exclusion in rural areas and to design appropriate interventions that improve social services and enhance social economy through a series of local "Smart Village Labs".

In the long run, you will indirectly benefit from the project's findings and results, particularly if you are a resident in one of the selected rural areas where the INSPIRE project members will launch interventions (e.g., fund local social services) that are expected to lead to practical improvements in the wellbeing of local communities. Moreover, by participating in the activity, you will also be connected to the project as key stakeholder, and you will be able to access first-hand our resources and results (e.g., digital tools, learning resources).

What we need from you: purpose of data collection

Note: *In this section the specific project activity and its purpose should be briefly explained. The following paragraph serves as an example for the INSPIRE T1.3 – National survey on meso-level factors driving social exclusion in European rural areas.*

We would like to learn more about your perceptions and beliefs around the drivers and the effects of national factors that drive social exclusion in rural areas in your country.

To effectively conduct this, we need to process some of your personal data:

- Your contact details;
- Some basic demographics (age, gender, income level);
- Your professional info (organisation, job position, field of expertise);
- Your opinions on the subject matter.

Note: *In case of an **interview or focus group**, for which you must keep a record, you must **make sure to include the following statement:***

This study involves the audio or video recording of your interview/focus group discussion. The recorded file will only be locally stored by the partner conducting the activity, and will be erased once accurately transcribed. Neither your name nor any other identifying information (such as your voice or picture) will be used in presentations or in written products resulting from this interview.

What will we do with your data?

The information you provide will be confidential. Your consent form will be kept separate from the observations collected during the course of the project activity. We will share your data with a few other INSPIRE project partners that are involved in the data analysis and reporting process. Once the data is analysed, a report of the findings may be submitted for publication. The project's deliverables that will be derived by this activity will **not include your personal data or any other information that could identify you.**

The results of this project activity may be shared with European Union representatives (e.g., the Project Officer evaluating the project's progress, auditing EU agencies). Only broad trends will be reported, and **it will not be possible to identify any individuals.** We will not share your data with 3rd parties. Data will be accessible to the project team of [\[name of organisation conducting the activity\]](#).

Detailed information on how the INSPIRE project handles data is provided at the **INSPIRE Privacy Policy** document that was shared with you *or* can be found online here: [\[link to online pdf on INSPIRE website\]](#).

Are there any ethical risks involved?

The INSPIRE project was **evaluated as “ethics-ready” by the European Commission.** Therefore, no ethical risks are involved in the project's activity.

Furthermore, the project has recruited an **Ethics Mentor**, who provides advises on ethics-related aspects of the project's activities. These advises were taken into consideration for the design and implementation of the project's activity.

Finally, the project has obtained an Ethical Clearance by the Ethics Committee of the CITY College, University of York Europe Campus. The Ethical Clearance applies in this project's activity.

Are there any risks involved?

No risks are involved.

Does my participation entail financial costs?

No financial costs are entailed in your participation.

Access, deletion of information or consent withdrawal

According to General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), you have the right to ask us to: (i) give you a copy of your data, (ii) correct your data, if you think they are not accurate, (iii) erase your data, (iv) limit or stop processing applied to your data, or (v) give you your data in an appropriate format and to transfer them to another organisation. You may also withdraw your consent and, therefore, your participation at any time without consequences. Anonymous data already collected will be used because we cannot trace the information back to you. No further data would be collected, or any other procedure would be carried out in relation to your information.

In case you wish to verify the personal data that we store, have it modified, corrected, deleted or request a consent withdrawal, you may communicate with the responsible partner listed below and

ask a copy of the **INSPIRE Data Subject Request Form**. Please fill in the form, explicitly describing your request, and forward it back to the partner conducting the project activity.

Whom do I contact if there is a need to?

INSPIRE partner conducting the project activity		INSPIRE Project Coordinator	
Partner name:	Please include contact details of partner conducting the activity	Partner name:	WHITE RESEARCH SRL
Contact person:	--/--	Contact persons:	Thomas Bakratsas Danai Antonaki
Phone:	--/--	Phone:	+32 2 520 00 09
Email:	--/--	Email:	tbakratsas@white-research.eu dantonaki@white-research.eu
Website	--/--	Website	http://white-research.eu

Informed Consent Form

“I confirm that I understand that by ticking each box below I am consenting to this element of the study. I understand that it will be assumed that unticked boxes mean that I DO NOT consent to that part of the study. I understand that by not giving consent for any one element, I may be deemed ineligible for participating in this project’s activity.

I confirm that I have been given a **full explanation of the purpose** of the project’s activity. I have **[read and]** **understood the Information Sheet** which I was provided with or listened to an explanation about the project by a project partner. (If you do not tick the box of this question, please do not proceed with this consent form until you are fully aware of what your participation in the project will mean).

In case the research participant cannot read and/or sign the Information Sheet as it is, a verbal consent that is either audio/video-recorded (the recorded item must be stored) or given with the presence of a witness suffices for their participation in the research activity (relevant evidence must be secured for the verbal consent). In that case, the description must be adapted according to the research participant. This condition does not apply in cases in which research participants are minors or have severe mental disabilities (such as dementia): we therefore strongly encourage to exclude these target groups from our research scope.

In the case the research participant cannot read and/or sign the Information Sheet as it is, a mitigation mechanism must be secured. Examples include the engagement of experts in sign language or the recruitment of a translator, who will assist the research participant to understand the information sheet and provide consent.

I have had an **opportunity to consider** what information will be expected of me. I have also had the **opportunity to ask questions** which have been answered to my satisfaction.

I agree to appear in **pictures/videos** that may be taken during the activity as evidence of the activity itself and as possible promotional material for the INSPIRE project. I understand that these pictures will not be provided to any organisations for commercial purposes. However, they may be processed by third parties as a consequence of their dissemination at international level through the project’s social media accounts (e.g., LinkedIn) and website.

I understand that the consortium has no control on the images after dissemination.

I agree that my **anonymised/pseudonymised research data** may be used by others for future research.
(I will not be identifiable when this data is shared).

I understand that my **participation is voluntary** and that I am **free to withdraw** at any time without giving a reason, and that any data after the time of which it is withdrawn will be no longer be included as part of any future reports, unless I agree otherwise.

I understand that my **personal data will be held and processed in confidence** and in accordance with the principles laid out by **GDPR**.

I understand and agree that the project research team and other authorised researchers may use my data in publications, reports, and other research outputs, only if they agree to **preserve the confidentiality of the information** as requested in this form.

I am aware of whom I should **contact** if I have **questions about this activity**.

I am aware of whom I should **contact** if I want to access the **transcribed content** of my interview. **[applicable in interviews and focus groups]**

I am aware of whom I should **contact** if I wish to **lodge a complaint** or if I want **my personal data deleted**.

I confirm that I have **[read and]** **understood the above and freely consent to participate in this project’s activity**. I have been given adequate time to consider my participation.”

Same as above. In case the research participant cannot read the Information Sheet, a verbal consent that is given with the presence of a witness suffices for their participation in the research activity (relevant evidence must be secured for the verbal consent).

Future activities

If you would like your contact details to be retained so that you can be contacted in the future by the project researchers who would like to invite you to participate in **further activities of this project**, or in future studies of a similar nature, please tick the appropriate box below.

Yes, I would be happy to be contacted in this way*

No, I would not like to be contacted

*Contact details

Email:.....**(please include your email address in case you wish to be contacted for future activities)**

Name of participant

Date

Signature

Annex 3: INSPIRE Data Subject Request Form

This form should be used to submit a data subject request under the provisions of the European Union General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Submitter details

Name:	[xx]
Surname:	[xx]
E-mail:	[xx]
Address:	[xx]
Name:	[xx]

Type of request

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Consent withdrawal | <input type="checkbox"/> Restriction of processing of personal data |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Access request | <input type="checkbox"/> Personal data portability request |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Rectification of personal data | <input type="checkbox"/> Objection to processing of personal data |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Erasure of personal data | <input type="checkbox"/> Request regarding automated decision making and profiling |

Personal data involved

Request details

Request reason/justification

Name Surname:

Signature:

Date:

Once completed, this form should be submitted via e-mail, using the following contact details:

Note: Contact details of the partner that is conducting the project's activity will always be provided in section below. The following table serves as an example.

INSPIRE consortium partner	WHITE RESEARCH
Contact person	XXXX
Phone	+32 2 520 00 09
Email	XXXX
Address	Avenue de la Toison d'Or 67, 1060, Brussels, Belgium
Website	www.white-research.eu

inspire
SMART VILLAGE LABS

GA 101136592

PARTNERS

@inspire-project

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